

Systematic literature review protocol for biosecurity, culling, vaccination, and movement restriction measures for 25 vector-borne diseases

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1. Background

Vector-borne diseases (VBDs) of animals, transmitted by arthropod vectors such as mosquitoes, biting midges, flies, and ticks, have increasingly affected the European Union (EU) over the past decades. Some VBDs, including bluetongue, West Nile fever, and lumpy skin disease, are already present in the EU, while others, such as Rift Valley fever and African horse sickness, pose an ongoing risk at EU borders. The geographic expansion of competent vectors, influenced by climate and ecological changes, increases the likelihood of introduction and spread of these diseases. Several VBD vectors, including *Aedes* mosquitoes and sandflies, can also transmit zoonotic pathogens, highlighting the relevance of these diseases for both animal and public health.

Previous EFSA scientific opinions, including assessments in 2017 and 2020, and the listing of twelve VBDs under the Animal Health Law, demonstrate the need for up-to-date information on surveillance, prevention, and control measures.

In January 2025, EFSA received a mandate from the European Commission to provide updated scientific advice on VBDs, including mapping and assessing the effectiveness of current surveillance, prevention, and control measures.

The current protocol describes the methodology used to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) to compile and map available evidence on prevention and control measures for listed and non-listed VBDs of interest (Table 1) in the EU, such as vaccination, culling, movement restrictions or on farm biosecurity measures, including evidence on their effectiveness, to inform EFSA's risk assessment and recommendations.

Table 1. Vector-borne disease (VBD) agents included in the SLR

Abbreviation	Vector-borne disease agent
AHSV	African horse sickness virus
AKAV	Akabane virus
BTV	Bluetongue virus
<i>B. burgdorferi</i>	<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i>
BEFV	Bovine ephemeral fever virus
Besnoitia	Besnoitia
CanL	<i>Leishmania infantum</i>
<i>C. burnetii</i>	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
CCHFV	Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus
CVV	Bunyamwera virus
EEEV/WEEV	Eastern/Western equine encephalitis virus
EHD	Epizootic haemorrhagic disease virus
EIAV	Equine infectious anaemia virus
JEV	Japanese encephalitis virus
LSDV	Lumpy skin disease virus
RVFV	Rift Valley fever virus
SBV	Schmallenberg virus
SHUV	Shuni virus
SLEV	St. Louis encephalitis virus
TBEV	Tickborne encephalitis
<i>T. evansi</i>	<i>Trypanosoma evansi</i>
<i>T. vivax</i>	<i>Trypanosoma vivax</i>
VEE	Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus
VSAV	Vesicular stomatitis viruses
WNV	West Nile virus

2. Objective and Review questions

The objective of this SLR was to answer the following question:

“What is the available evidence on the effectiveness of prevention and control measures for the VBDs of interest?”

This was addressed through the following specific review questions:

- 1) What is the effectiveness of *movement restrictions* in reducing transmission of any of the VBDs in an animal population?
- 2) For those diseases for which *vaccines* are available, what is the documented effectiveness of the vaccines?

- 3) What is the effectiveness of *culling* in reducing transmission of any of the VBDs in an animal population?
- 4) What is the effectiveness of specific on-farm *biosecurity measures* in reducing transmission of any of the VBDs in an animal population?

The following studies were considered out of scope, and *not* included in the scope of this SLR:

- Studies of vaccine efficacy (evaluation of vaccine performance in controlled, laboratory experiments), which are already systematically reviewed in a complementary SLR¹.
- Measures targeting vectors only, without reporting effectiveness on preventing transmission of the VBDs of interest in host animals.
- Medicinal treatments to prevent or cure the VBDs.

3. Study selection

3.1. Information source

Scopus was used as the primary platform for literature searches.

3.2. Search strategy

The general search strategy was combination of three elements: String 1: agent/disease description; String 2: keywords representing all the risk mitigation measures in scope; String 3: restriction criteria for the type of study and year of publication. Details are given in Table 2:

Table 2. General search criteria applied

#	Search string
1	Disease for: AHSV, AKAV, BTV, Bburgdorferi, BEFV, CVV, Cburnetii, CCHFV, EHDV, EEEV/WEEV, JEV, CanL, LSDV, RVFV, SBV, SHUV, SLEV, TBEV, VEEV, VSAV, WNV, Tevansi, Tvivax, EIAV, Besnoitia

¹ Dórea, F.C. Swanenburg M, Horigan V, Han S, Young B, de Freitas Costa E, de Souza Santos M.A., Evans D, Royall E, Aznar I, Dhollander S, 2022. Data collection for risk assessments on animal health: review protocol 2021. EFSA supporting publication 2022:EN-7086. 47 pp.doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7086

	Example for AHSV: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("African horse sickness" OR "Pestis Equorum" Or "Peste Equina")
2	AND (mitigation OR culling OR "stamping out" OR "control measure*" OR "contingency measure*" OR "preventive measure*" OR "control intervention*" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak* control" OR "epidemic*" OR "reduce* transmission" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemiological model*" OR "mathematical model*" OR biosecurity OR "movement restrict*")
3	AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))

Unique search strings were generated for each individual VBD agent. For Akabane virus and Shuni virus only a limited number of studies were available, thus the second string was removed to retrieve as many papers as possible in the SLR. In contrast, for diseases agents with extensive research, additional exclusion keywords were applied to increase specificity.

Generally, the additional keywords excluded studies targeting humans. This was the case for BTV, *B. burgdorferi*, *C. burnetii*, CCHFV, EEEV, WEEV, JEV, *L. infantum*, TBEV, VSAV and WNV. All final search strings used for each VBDs are provided in Annex I.

3.3. Reference management

Full references and abstracts were downloaded from Scopus in RIS format and uploaded into the Systematic Literature Review software DistillerSR® (Evidence Partners).

3.4. Study screening

Figure 1. Systematic Literature Review (SLR) workflow for selecting eligible articles.

3.4.1. Level 1 screening

To meet the review objective, the study inclusion criteria were based on the Population – Intervention – Comparison – Outcome (PICO) strategy (Table 3):

Table 3. PICO strategy for level 1 screening of literature on effectiveness of risk mitigation measures against 25 vectors-borne diseases.

Population:	Animal species present in the EU and susceptible to one or more of the following diseases: AHSV, AKAV, Besnoitia, BTV, <i>B. burgdorferi</i> , BEFV, <i>L. infantum</i> , CVV, <i>C. burnetii</i> , CCHFV, EIAV, EHDV, EEEV/WEEV, JEVV, LSDV, RVF, SBV, SHUV, SLEV, TBEV, <i>T. evansi</i> , <i>T. vivax</i> , VEEV, VSAV, WNV
Intervention:	Prevention or control measure: movement restrictions, vaccination, culling and on farm biosecurity
Comparison:	Not applicable (not assessed in Level 1)
Outcome:	Any outcome related to the effectiveness of the measure

The screening process was conducted using the DistillerSR® which allowed independent screening by multiple reviewers in a blinded process.

In the Level 1 screening, reviewers were presented with title and abstract. In line with the PICO strategy (Table 3), reviewers applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in Ttable 4).

Table 4. Eligibility and exclusion criteria applied in Level 1 screening (title and abstract review).

Element	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Publication type	Primary research studies	Secondary information, such as reviews
Language	English	Not English
Population	Studies targeting animal species susceptible to the diseases of interest Studies targeting vectors which report results related to cases prevented, reduction in disease prevalence, transmission, etc	Studies targeting vectors which report results related to the reduction in vector presence/vector mortality only Studies in humans
Intervention	Studies evaluating movement restrictions, vaccination, culling or on farm biosecurity	
Study type	Field studies with results at the population level such as:	Experimental studies such as:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccine tested at population level, with results such as cases prevented or reduction in transmission. • Outbreak reports which could describe how outbreak was controlled • Modeling studies that include assessment of risk mitigation measures based on real data 	<p>Vaccine development, in vitro studies, laboratory experiments, test in controlled trials.</p> <p>Diagnostic test development, testing</p> <p>Phylogenetic, genotyping studies unless for evaluating mitigation measures</p> <p>Mathematical models based on theoretical parameters that were not validated using field data</p>
Study design	Case-control and cohort studies, and cross-sectional/surveys when risk factors were studied	Seroprevalence studies without any studies of risk factors that could be targeted for risk mitigation

Using these criteria as guidance, reviewers marked papers as:

- **Eligible:** paper met all inclusion criteria and none of the exclusion criteria. These papers were included in the next level of screening.
- **Addresses a risk mitigation measure but the disease is not in scope.** These papers were flagged but not included in the next phases.
- **Addresses a risk mitigation measure applied in vectors only.** These papers were flagged but not included in the next phases.
- **Not eligible:** Article was not about the effectiveness of risk mitigation measures in animal or vector populations. These papers were excluded from the SLR.
- **Not sure:** if the information provided in the abstract was enough to answer the question of eligibility, reviewers marked the papers as “not sure”, including them for screening in the next phase.

Any articles considered eligible by at least one reviewer were included, whereas articles were rejected when it was the consensus decision of two independent reviewers. Articles in which reviewers were not sure or only one reviewer voted on inclusion were reviewed in phase 2.

3.4.2. Level 2 screening

Articles included in Level 1 screening were evaluated in a second phase, based on full-text. The same inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in Table 4 were applied, with further specification of the criteria based on the type of risk mitigation measure addressed (Tables 5 to 8). All exclusions were documented with the reason for exclusion.

Phase 2 only considered papers in which the effectiveness of the risk mitigation measure was measured and reported with evaluation of the statistical significance of the results observed. Studies which investigated risk/protective factors that could be considered as risk mitigation measures were also included.

Table 5. Eligibility criteria for vaccination effectiveness.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publication type	Primary research studies	Reviews
Language	English	Not English
Population	Studies targeting animal species susceptible to the diseases of interest for which licenced vaccines are available	Not susceptible population
Intervention	Vaccination with vaccines authorised or used in the EU. Includes emergency or mass vaccination campaigns under EU or national control programmes.	Studies evaluating experimental formulations not applicable to EU serotypes; studies addressing only other control measures (e.g., vector control, movement bans) without vaccination.
Comparison	Unvaccinated populations, different vaccination strategies (coverage, serotype, or timing), or historical pre-vaccination data from the same region.	No comparator or insufficient description of vaccination status.
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in VBD incidence or prevalence • Reduction in outbreak frequency, number of infected holdings, or transmission between farms. • Evidence of herd immunity or reduced basic reproduction number (R_0 / R_t). <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in clinical disease, morbidity, or mortality. • Decrease in viral load or viremia in vaccinated animals. • Reduced pathogen detection in vectors. • Duration of immunity and seroconversion rates. • Adverse effects or vaccine safety. 	Studies reporting only immunogenicity or antibody titres without epidemiological endpoints; modelling studies lacking empirical field data.

Study design	Field trials, observational and quasi-experimental studies, outbreak investigations, and data-driven modelling relevant to EU epidemiological conditions.	Reviews, conference abstracts or purely theoretical models without field validation.
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Table 6. Eligibility criteria for movement restrictions.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publication type	Primary research studies	Reviews
Language	English	Not English
Population	Studies targeting animal species infected with or exposed to any of the selected vector-borne diseases	Not susceptible population, not infected population
Intervention	Implementation of movement restrictions on live animals, animal products as part of outbreak control or prevention measures. Includes local, regional, or national movement bans, zoning, compartmentalization, or temporary trade restrictions.	Studies assessing only other control measures (e.g., vaccination, culling, or vector control) without a movement restriction component, or purely theoretical proposals without implementation evidence.
Comparison	Areas, herds, or populations not subject to movement restrictions; or pre-/post-intervention data from the same region. Comparisons may include alternative mitigation strategies.	Studies lacking a comparator, baseline, or sufficient description of the control context.
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in VBD incidence or prevalence. • Reduction in outbreak frequency, spread, or number of infected holdings. • Decrease in between-farm or between-region transmission. • Evidence of reduced R_0 or R_t values. <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration and effectiveness of restriction periods. • Unintended consequences (e.g., animal welfare, trade, economic, or logistical impacts). 	Studies reporting only qualitative perceptions or unrelated outcomes without epidemiological endpoints.

Study design	Observational studies (cohort, case-control, before–after), outbreak investigations, and quantitative modelling studies that incorporate empirical field data.	Narrative reviews, theoretical models without validation using field data
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Table 7. Eligibility criteria for culling effectiveness.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publication type	Primary research studies	Reviews
Language	English	Not English
Population	Studies targeting animal species infected with or exposed to any of the selected vector-borne diseases	Not susceptible population, not infected population
Intervention	Partial or complete culling of infected or exposed herds implemented as part of official or emergency outbreak control or eradication programmes. Includes depopulation, stamping-out, or targeted culling strategies.	Studies evaluating only other control measures (e.g., vaccination, vector control, movement restrictions) without a culling component, or where culling was not implemented as an intentional disease mitigation strategy.
Comparison	Non-culled or partially culled populations, regions, or herds (with or without additional control measures); or historical data from pre- or post-culling periods within the same outbreak or geographical area.	Studies lacking a comparator, baseline, or sufficient description of the control context.
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in VBD incidence or prevalence • Reduction in outbreak frequency, number of infected holdings, or transmission between farms. <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced pathogen detection in vectors. • Adverse effects or unintended consequences of culling (e.g. animal welfare, economic, or ecological impacts). 	Studies reporting only qualitative perceptions or unrelated outcomes (e.g., carcass disposal logistics) without epidemiological endpoints.

Study design	Field investigations, observational (cohort, case-control, before-after) studies, outbreak reports, or quantitative modelling studies incorporating empirical EU field data.	Narrative reviews, theoretical models without validation using field data,
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Table 8. Eligibility Criteria for on farm biosecurity effectiveness.

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publication type	Primary research studies	Reviews
Language	English	Not English
Population	Studies targeting animal species susceptible to the diseases of interest raised in any type of farming system	Not susceptible population
Intervention	Biosecurity measures implemented in farms	Studies reporting biosecurity measures without evaluation of effectiveness; studies evaluating biosecurity measures not implemented at farm level (measures adopted before farm establishment)
Comparison	Status before intervention;	
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in VBD incidence or prevalence • Reduction in outbreak frequency, number of infected holdings, or transmission between farms. • Reduction of disease risk of introduction and spread <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in clinical disease, morbidity, or mortality. • Decrease in viral load or viremia in animals raised in farms that implement biosecurity. • Reduced pathogen detection in vectors. 	Studies reporting only implementation of biosecurity measures without assessment of efficacy

	• Evidence of improved flock health	
Study design	Observational and cross-sectional studies, risk factor analysis, outbreak investigations and surveys.	Reviews, conference abstracts or purely theoretical models without field validation.

3.5. Data extraction

All studies included after Level 2 screening were subjected to data collection.

Data extraction was performed systematically using structured data forms set up in DistillerSR®. Data from each study was collected by a single reviewer. All reviewers working on the project went through a harmonisation exercise first, where reviewers read the same paper, and discussed together the data collection.

All the variables included in the data collection, and the structure of the form, are available in Annex II.

3.6. Analysis and report

All data collected using DistillerSR® were downloaded as comma separated values (CSV) files, and analysed in the statistical programming environment R (<https://www.R-project.org/>), or summarised by reviewers.

Annex I – Full search strings for each individual VBD

Tag	string after scoping
AHS	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((“African horse sickness” OR “Pestis Equorum” Or “Peste Equina”) AND (culling OR “stamping out” OR “control interventions” OR “disease control” OR “outbreak*” OR “epidemic*” OR transmission OR “epidemiological model” OR “mathematical model” OR “animal euthanasia” OR vaccinat* OR “control measures” OR “infection control” OR “risk factors” OR “epidemic model” OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))
AKAV	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((“African horse sickness” OR “Pestis Equorum” Or “Peste Equina”) AND (culling OR “stamping out” OR “control interventions” OR “disease control” OR “outbreak*” OR “epidemic*” OR transmission OR “epidemiological model” OR “mathematical model” OR “animal euthanasia” OR vaccinat* OR “control measures” OR “infection control” OR “risk factors” OR “epidemic model” OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))
BTV	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((bluetongue OR "Psuedo Foot and mouth disease") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity) ANDNOT ("experimental infection")) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Cell") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Gene Sequence") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Nucleotide Sequence") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Phylogeny"))
Bburgdorferi	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Lyme" OR "Lyme borreliosis" OR "Borrelia burgdorferi" OR "erythema migrans") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool"))
BEFV	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((“Bovine ephemeral fever” OR “Bovine Epizootic Fever” OR "Three Day Sickness" OR "Ephemeral Fever" OR "Three-Day Sickness" OR "Three-Day Stiffsickness" OR "Dragon Boat Disease" OR "Lazy Man’s Disease" OR "Dengue of Cattle") AND (culling OR “stamping out” OR “control interventions” OR “disease control” OR “outbreak*” OR “epidemic*” OR transmission OR “epidemiological model” OR “mathematical model” OR “animal euthanasia” OR vaccinat* OR “control measures” OR “infection control” OR “risk factors” OR “epidemic model” OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))

CVV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Bunyamwera virus" OR "Bunyamwera orthobunyavirus") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))
Cburnetii	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Q-fever" OR "Query fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Coxiellosis" OR "Nine Mile fever" OR "Abattoir fever") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Very Elderly") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Preschool Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Infant") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged, 80 And Over") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human"))
CCHFV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Crimean Congo haemorrhagic fever" OR "Crimean Congo hemorrhagic fever" OR "Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever" OR "Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever" OR "Congo Fever" OR "Cache Valley") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Male") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Myalgia") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vomiting") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice"))
EHD	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Epizootic haemorrhagic disease" OR "Epizootic hemorrhagic disease" OR "Ibaraki disease" OR "Epizootic haemorrhagic virus" OR "Epizootic hemorrhagic virus") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))

EEEV, WEEV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("equine encephalomyelitis" OR "equine encephalitis" OR "Eastern encephalitis" OR "Western encephalitis") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred Balb C") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Hamster") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mus")))
JEV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Japanese encephalitis") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Infant") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Preschool Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Bcg Vaccine") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Measles") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Measles Mumps Rubella Vaccine") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Headache") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Case Report") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Rubella") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Pertussis") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mumps") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human")))
CanL	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Leishmania infantum") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Male") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Experiment") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Leishmania Donovanii") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred Balb C") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Leishmania Braziliensis") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Bagg Albino Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "In Vitro Study") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Infant") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Th1 Cell")))

LSD	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("lumpy skin") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Experiment") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Isolation And Purification") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Dna Extraction") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Whole Genome Sequencing") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mdbk Cell Line") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Cytopathogenic Effect")))
RVF	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Rift Valley fever") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Dengue Virus") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Dengue") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human Cell") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Chikungunya") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Ebola Hemorrhagic Fever") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged, 80 And Over") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans")))
SBV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Schmallenberg virus" OR "Schmallenberg disease") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")))
SHUV	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Shuni virus") AND (PUBYEAR > 1990)
SLEV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Saint Louis encephalitis" OR "St. Louis Encephalitis" OR st AND louis AND encephalitis) AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vero Cells") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Preschool Child")))

TBEV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("tick-borne encephalitis" OR "TBE" OR "Russian spring-summer encephalitis" OR "Biundulant meningoencephalitis" OR "Central European encephalitis" OR "Biphasic milk fever" OR "Diphasic milk fever") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Experiment") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child, Preschool") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged, 80 And Over")))
VEE	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Venezuelan equine encephalitis" OR "Venezuelan equine fever") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Replicon") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred Balb C") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human Cell") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vero Cells") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vero Cell Line") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "In Vitro Study") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred C57bl"))
VSAV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("Vesicular stomatitis") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Experiment") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human Cell") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Cell Line") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Virus Recombinant") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vero Cell Line") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred Balb C") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "In Vitro Study") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Vero Cells") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred C57bl") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human Immunodeficiency Virus 1") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Hek293t Cell Line") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Hiv-1") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Hek293 Cells") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Hamster"))

WNV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("West Nile fever") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Middle Aged") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Child") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Aged, 80 And Over") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Young Adult") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Case Report") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Infant") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Chikungunya") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Zika Fever") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Dengue Virus") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Human") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Humans") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Animal Experiment") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mouse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "Mice, Inbred C57bl"))
Tevansi	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((surra OR "Tevansi" OR "T.evansi" OR "T. evansi" OR "Trypanosoma evansi" OR "Trypanosoma brucei evans" OR "Spirochaeta evansi" OR "Trypanozoon evansi" OR "Trypanosomas evansi") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))
Tvivax	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((Tvivax OR "Trypanosoma vivax" OR "T.vivax" OR "T. vivax" OR "Trypanosoma caprae" OR "Trypanosoma angolense" OR Nagana) AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))
EIAV	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("EIAV" OR "Equine Infectious Anemia" OR "swamp fever" OR "slow fever" OR Coggins) AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))
Besnoitia	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((Besnoitiosis OR Besnoitia OR "elephant skin disease") AND (culling OR "stamping out" OR "control interventions" OR "disease control" OR "outbreak*" OR "epidemic*" OR transmission OR "epidemiological model" OR "mathematical model" OR "animal euthanasia" OR vaccinat* OR "control measures" OR "infection control" OR "risk factors" OR "epidemic model" OR mitigation OR biosecurity)) AND (PUBYEAR > 1990) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

Annex II – Structured forms used for data collection

Variable	Expected data types and description
Reviewer	Person who reviewed the paper
Article author	First author
Publication Year	Publication year
Title	Full title of the article
Reference ID	Unique reference ID
Country	Country where study was performed
Year study started	Year the study was conducted (start)
Year study ended	Year the study ended
VBD agent	Causative agent of vector borne diseases
Agent subtype type	Details of type of agent, categorical ("genotype", "serotype", "strain", "subspecies", "Other")
Agent subtype details	further information regarding the subtype (e.g., 'BTV-8', 'genotype 1a')
Study ID	Identifier to differentiate unique groups within a paper, starting at 1. If a study has multiple study groups (e.g., different species, treatments, or comparisons within the same paper), then data is collected individual for each group, and this ID is used to identify data collection forms belonging to the same group.
Study group description	Description of the specific study group if different treatments were received (e.g., 'Vaccinated cattle', 'Control group sheep', 'Treatment A horses')
Target Host	List of target host species, categorical (with option to add "Other" and enter species as free-text)
Target Vector	Vector group (Vector-targeted studies only, categorical ["mosquitoes", "midges", "sandflies", "ticks", "biting flies"])
Target Vector details	Vector species (e.g. 'Aedes albopictus', 'Culicoides scoticus')
Population Size	Size of the population studied for the specific animal group for which data is being collected.
Sampling Strategy	sampling strategy used to select sampling units in the study. categorical (with option to add "Other" and enter species as free-text) ["Census", "Convenience sampling", "Objective (random) sampling", "Purposeful sampling", "Randomized Control Trial (RCT)", "Selective (risk-based) sampling", "Suspect sampling", "Unspecified", "OUTBREAK - selecting all cases", "OUTBREAK - selecting all NON-cases", "Other"]
Sampling Unit	Type of unit sampled in the study (holding, herd, individual/animal, other)
Sample size	Number of units in the sampled group (e.g., number of herds)
Group type: cases or controls (positive or negative)	Data refers to cases (POS) or negative units (NEG)
Outcome Indicator	Outcome/effect measure used. Categorical (with option to add "Other" and enter species as free-text) ["Disease Cases", "Serologically positive", "Deaths", "Other"]
Laboratory test	Diagnostic laboratory test used to confirm infection or presence of antibodies.
Laboratory test description	Additional details regarding the laboratory test (for instance commercial names, methodology used, cut-off values for interpretation)

Laboratory test target	Target of laboratory test. Categorical (with option to add “Other” and enter species as free-text) ["Nucleic acid", "Antigen", "Antibody", "Virus", "Bacterium/Rickettsia", "Parasite", "CLINICAL SIGNS", "DEATHS", "Not applicable", "Other"]
Unit at which diagnostic is made	Level of aggregation for case definition Categorical (with option to add “Other” and enter species as free-text) ["Animal (individual)", "Herd", "Geographical Unit", "Other"]
Risk Factor Category	Which one of the 4 RMM categories does the risk factor fall in? Categorical ["Biosecurity", "Vaccination", "Movement control", "Culling"]
Risk Factor	Risk/protective factor investigated, describe as in the paper.
Effect Measure Type	Type of effect measure reported. Categorical (with option to add “Other” and enter species as free-text) ["Odds Ratio", "Model Coefficient", "Other"]
Effect Value	Numerical effect measure reported
Confidence interval – lower limit	Lower limit for the reported confidence interval for the effect.
Confidence interval – upper limit	Higher limit for the reported confidence interval for the effect.
P-value	P-value reported for the effect value, when given.
<i>Specific for vaccine studies</i>	
Vaccine Name	Name of the vaccine used
Vaccine Type	Type of vaccine. Categorical (with option to add “Other” and enter species as free-text) ["Inactivated (dead)", "Live attenuated", "Live recombinant", "Recombinant (subunit vaccines)", "Other"]
Serotypes in Vaccine	Monovalent or Polyvalent vaccine type
Serotypes List	List of specific serotypes in the vaccine
Vaccine Route	Method of vaccine administration
Vaccine Regimen	Regimen of application (doses, intervals, etc.)
Units Vaccinated	Number/percentage of units vaccinated in the specific group
Vaccination Units Type	Units used for vaccination count
Vaccine Efficacy	Vaccine efficacy as percentage
Vaccine Coverage	Protection coverage achieved as percentage
Vaccine Study Design	Retrospective or Prospective
Vaccine Effect Reported	Any details of vaccine effect, success measures, assessment methods
<i>Specific for modelling studies</i>	
Risk Mitigation Measure	Risk mitigation measure assessed in model. Categorical with the option of adding free-text when choosing other ["Vaccination", "Movement control restriction", "Culling", "Other"]
Model Parameters	List of parameters used in the model
Model Data Sources	Fata sources used for model parameterization
Effect Reported	Summary of the risk mitigation measure's effect as reported
<i>Quality control and additional information</i>	
	<i>Quality control and additional information</i>
Study Limitations	Study main limitations as reported

Additional Comments	Other comments or notes about the study or data extraction
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Annex III – Systematic literature review biosecurity results

Table 1. Color categories for biosecurity summary table interpretation.

Risk/protective factor category	Category colour
Farm management	Blue
Animal Movement & Trade	Orange
Veterinary & Disease management	Red
Biosecurity & Hygiene	Teal
Pasture management	Green
Reproduction and Parturition management	Purple

Table 2. Summary table of identified biosecurity-related risk and/or protective factors for 25 pathogens.

Pathogen	Category	Biosecurity measure Reported effectiveness [quantitative value]	Target species	Interpretation of biosecurity measure effect	Reference(s)	SUMMARY
African horse sickness (AHSV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Akabane virus (AKAV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Cache Valley virus (CVV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Eastern equine encephalitis virus (EEEV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Western equine encephalitis virus (WEEV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Saint Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Shuni virus (SHUV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV)						No eligible papers found (SLR=0)
<i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i>	Access to shelter	No presence of shelter associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.46, 95% CI 1.05-5.73]	Equines	Access to shelter is protective	(Gutierrez-Exposito et al., 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In equines, shelter access and rodent control were found protective (Gutierrez-Exposito et al., 2017).
	Pest and rodent control	No rodent control program associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 5.34, 95% CI 1.95-14.62]	Equines	Rodent control is protective	(Gutierrez-Exposito et al., 2017)	
	Handling of sick or dead animals	Time in housing with seropositive cows associated with higher seroprevalence [Model coefficient 0.229, p = 0.004]	Cattle	Longer housing with more seropositive animals increases seroconversion risk	(Esteban-Gil et al., 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In cattle, housing with seropositive animals (Esteban-Gil et al., 2017) and frequent external

	Visitors/vets/suppliers	Farm workers exchange visits of neighboring farms (within few kilometers) more than two to three times a week associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 5.01, 95% CI 1.08-23.22]	Cattle	Frequent farm worker visits to other farms is a risk factor	(Talafha et al., 2015)	worker visits (Talafha et al., 2015) increased risk, whereas frequent cleaning reduced seroconversion risk (Talafha et al., 2015).
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Frequency of cleaning (Once a day, twice a day, once a month) associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.086, 95% CI 0.01-0.73]	Cattle	Frequent farm cleaning is protective	(Talafha et al., 2015)	
Bluetongue virus (BTV)	Herds combining multiple species	Herding animals with other species (ruminants, cats and dogs, equines) associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.584, 95% CI 0.345-0.99]	Camel	Herds combining multiple species is associated with lower seroprevalence	(Al-Mamari et al., 2025)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In camelids, one study showed a protective effect of mixing species in herds (Al-Mamari et al., 2025). • In ruminants, one study demonstrated contact with other herds as a risk factor (Torsson et al., 2017), while the contact with wildlife or other animals were not conclusive three studies (Torsson et al., 2017; Selim et al., 2023; Adam et al., 2014).
	Contact with other herds	Interaction with other domestic herds associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.85, 95% CI 1.55-10.5]	Goat, sheep	Contact with other herds is a risk factor	(Torsson et al., 2017)	
	Contact with other animals	Interaction with wildlife has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2014 [OR = 0.57, 95% CI 0.03-7.61] • In 2015 [OR = 1.18, 95% CI 0.48-2.94] 	Goat, sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Torsson et al., 2017)	
		Presence of other animals on the farm has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.4, 95% CI 0.94-2.1]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Selim et al., 2023)	
		No other animals Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.2, 95% CI 0.45-3.2]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Adam et al., 2014)	
	Access to shelter	Use of sheepfold associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.36, 95% CI 0.15-0.86]	Sheep	Use of sheepfold is protective (access to shelter)	(Sbizera et al., 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, access to shelter was protective in 3 studies (Sbizera et al., 2024; Sana et al., 2022; Cappai et al., 2018) and inconclusive in one (Adam et al., 2014).
Housing indoor associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.72, 95% CI 0.58-0.88]		Sheep	Access to shelter is protective	(Sana et al., 2022)		

		Animals stored in shelter overnight associated with lower incidence of BTV-1 [OR = 0.752, 95% CI 0.642-0.881]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Overnight access to shelter is protective	(Cappai et al., 2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One study (Santman-Berends et al., 2010) showed that closing stable doors during the day was protective, but no conclusive effect was found for ventilation/use of windbreak curtains.
		Cattle kept indoors has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 2.79, 95% CI 0.62-14.28]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Adam et al., 2014)	
	Openness of shelters	Keeping stable doors CLOSED throughout the day (versus OPEN throughout the day) associated with 3.6% increase in herd seroprevalence [95% CI 0.3% to 7.1%, p = 0.03]	Cattle	Keeping stable doors closed is protective	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	
		Horizontal ventilation openings in side walls vs. no ventilation has no clear association with herd seroprevalence [p = 0.82]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	
		Horizontal ventilation openings + windbreak curtain vs. no ventilation has no clear association with herd seroprevalence [p = 0.07]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	
	Animal sourcing	Purchasing animals from local market instead of other farms Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.37, 95% CI 0.44-4.23]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Adam et al., 2014)	<p>In ruminants, sourcing new animals from outside the herd was identified as a risk factor in 4 studies (da Silva et al., 2018; Khair et al., 2014; Green et al., 2005; Pascual-Linaza et al., 2014), but the effect was not always significant (Pascual-Linaza et al., 2014; Adam et al., 2014; Torsson et al., 2017).</p>
		Animals are sourced from within- the farm instead of purchased Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 0.86, 95% CI 0.08-9.27]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Adam et al., 2014)	
		New cattle entering herd association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 2183, 95% CI 1619-2945]	Cattle	Introducing new animals into herd is a risk factor	(da Silva et al., 2018)	
		Animal is purchased from market or introduced from other herds associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.87, 95% CI 1.07-13.87]	Cattle	Sourcing animals outside the farm is a risk factor	(Khair et al., 2014)	
		Imported cattle from selected states [with increased serologic prevalence] associated with higher herd-level	Cattle	Importing cattle from zones with higher BTV exposure is a risk factor	(Green et al., 2005)	

		seroprevalence [OR = 14.3, 95% CI 1.51-135.73]				
		Introduction of new animals into herd has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 0.99, 95% CI 0.26-3.65]	Goat, sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Torsson et al., 2017)	
		Cattle introduced into a mixed sheep farm from other farms Has no clear association with risk for BTV-1 occurrence in herd [OR = 0.85, 95% CI 0.69-1.05]	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Pascual-Linaza et al., 2014)	
		Sheep introduced into farm from other farms associated with higher incidence of BTV-1 occurrence in herd [OR = 1.25, 95% CI 1.11-1.4]	Sheep	Introducing new animals into herd is a risk factor	(Pascual-Linaza et al., 2014)	
	Quarantine	No quarantine of newly purchased animals associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 4.05, 95% CI 2.12-7.59]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Quarantine is protective	(Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014)	In ruminants, quarantine of newly purchased animals had a protective effect (Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014).
	Travel history	Participation in events associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.296, 95% CI 0.119-0.735]	Camel	Participating in events is associated with lower seroprevalence	(Al-Mamari et al., 2025)	In camelids , one study found an association with seroprevalence in animals that participated in events (Al-Mamari et al., 2025).
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	No use of disinfectants on the farm has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.0, 95% CI 0.05-0.1]	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Hijazeen et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, presence of mud and manure was demonstrated as a risk factor in one study (Cappai et al., 2018). • In sheep the use of disinfectants was not conclusive (Hijazeen et al., 2020).
		Presence of mud and manure associated with higher incidence of BTV-1 [OR = 2.491, 95% CI 1.443-4.305]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Presence of mud and manure is a risk factor	(Cappai et al., 2018)	
	Grazing practices	Allowing the animals to graze during day and night (versus no grazing) associated with 13.6% increase in herd seroprevalence [95% CI 7.2-20.8]	Cattle	Animal grazing is a risk factor	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, the practice of pasture rotation was identified as protective (Cappai et al., 2018).

		<p>Allowing the animals to graze a few hours per day between milking (versus no grazing) associated with 5.6% increase in herd seroprevalence [95% CI 1.4-10.2]</p>	Cattle	Animal grazing is a risk factor	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In cattle, animal grazing was a risk factor in one study investigating different grazing regimens (Santman-Berends et al., 2010).
		<p>Allowing the animals to graze only during day (versus no grazing) associated with 11.4% increase in herd seroprevalence [95% CI 6-17.3]</p>	Cattle	Animal grazing is a risk factor	(Santman-Berends et al., 2010)	
		<p>Rotation practice of pasture areas-turnover of the ground (versus no turnover) associated with lower incidence of BTV-1 [OR = 0.071, 95% CI 0.061-0.086]</p>	Cattle, goat, sheep	Turnover of the ground is protective	(Cappai et al., 2018)	
	Disease detection and record-keeping	<p>Keeping a genealogical record/control associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.23, 95% CI 0.12-0.45]</p>	Sheep	Record keeping is protective	(Sbizera et al., 2024)	<p>In sheep, keeping a genealogical record was protective (Sbizera et al., 2024) and lack of veterinary services was a risk factor (Hijazeen et al., 2020)</p>
	Access to veterinary care	<p>Lack of veterinary services associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 10, 95% CI 3.5-13.2]</p>	Sheep	Limited access to veterinary care is a risk factor	(Hijazeen et al., 2020)	
Borrelia burgdorferi	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	<p>Poor hygienic measures associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.1, 95% CI 0.91-4.86]</p>	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Alruhaili et al., 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In horses, presence of trees was reported as significantly associated with seroprevalence in one study (Neely et al., 2021), but access to forested habitats was inconclusive. One study did not find any significant effect of hygienic measures (Alruhaili et al., 2024).
	Pasture type	<p>Access to forested habitats (versus no access) has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.11, 95% CI 0.31-3.99]</p>	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Neely et al., 2021)	
		<p>Presence of oak trees bordering or in pasture (prevention of grazing) (versus no prevention) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 7.31, 95% CI 1.83-29.15]</p>	Horse	Presence of trees on pasture is a risk factor	(Neely et al., 2021)	
	Access to shelter	<p>Type of housing: OUTDOOR (versus INDOOR) associated with lower disease incidence [OR = 0.146, 95% CI 0.057-0.374]</p>	Dog	Keeping dogs indoors is a risk factor	((Usman et al., 2022)	<p>In dogs, one study showed significant risk effect of indoor housing and recent travel history (Usman et al., 2022)</p>

	Travel history	Travel history within last 7 days associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 3.647, 95% CI 1.478-8.994]	Dog	Recent travel history is a risk factor	(Usman et al., 2022)	
Bovine ephemeral fever virus (BEFV)	Access to veterinary care	Lack of veterinary services associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 9, 95% CI 4-11]	Cattle	Limited access to veterinary care is a risk factor	(Hijazeen et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In cattle, lack of veterinary services was a risk factor in 1 study (Hijazeen et al., 2020). • Another study reported significant risk associated with inappropriate management of manure and interactions between farm workers (Mirzaie et al., 2017).
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Inappropriate management of manure associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR =3.14, 95% CI 1.08-9.16]	Cattle	Inappropriate management of manure is a risk factor	(Mirzaie et al., 2017)	
	Visitors/vets/suppliers	Communication between farm workers associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR =9.82, 95% CI 1.18-82.24]	Cattle	Interactions between farm workers is a risk factor	(Mirzaie et al., 2017)	
		Car entrance/exit (on farm) has no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR =1, 95% CI 0.99-1.08]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Mirzaie et al., 2017)	
Coxiella Burnetii	Quarantine	Control of new introduction associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.3, 95% CI 0.2-0.4]	Sheep	Following a quarantine protocol is protective	(Guesmi et al., 2023)	<p>Factors related to animal movement and trade:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, 2 studies show quarantine to have a protective effect (Guesmi et al., 2023; Paul et al., 2012), but this finding was not always significant (Meadows et al., 2015a), or even a risk factor (Barkallah et al., 2018). Additionally, animal sourcing from outside the herd was associated with higher seroprevalence 5 studies (Menadi et al., 2020; Boroduske et al., 2017; Obaidat & Kersh, 2017; van Engelen et al., 2014; Nusinovici et al., 2014) but the effect was not always significant (Welch et al., 2024; van Engelen et al., 2014; Schimmer et al., 2014; Meadows et al., 2015a).
		No quarantine of newly purchased animals associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.75, 95% CI 1.19-11.86]	Cattle	Following a quarantine protocol is protective	(Paul et al., 2012)	
		Quarantining new animals Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 0.23, 95% CI 0.05 – 1.08]	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
		Quarantine for new animals Associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence and presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 23.13, 95% CI 2.23-240.34]	Sheep	Quarantine of new animals is a risk factor	(Barkallah et al., 2018)	
	Travel history	No. of movements of the animal since its birth (from one herd to another and to slaughter) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.59, 95% CI 1.32-1.9]	Cattle	Frequent out-of-farm animal movements are a risk factor	(Paul et al., 2014)	
	Animal sourcing	Permanent goat additions in the previous 12 months has no clear association with seropositivity	Goats	Association is inconclusive	(Welch et al., 2024)	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No animals were added or animals added were kids [OR = 1.8, 95% CI 1 – 32] Pregnant does added [OR = 1.0, 95% CI 0.5 – 2.2] 					
	<p>Two or more locations from which cattle are purchased (versus up to 1) No clear association with herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 3.1, 95% CI 0.9-11.2]</p>	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(van Engelen et al., 2014)		
	<p>One annual supply address for ewes has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.49, 95% CI 0.94-13.01]</p>	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2014)		
	<p>Two or more annual supply addresses for ewes has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.89, 95% CI 0.84-17.99]</p>	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2014)		
	<p>Purchasing animals from sales barn has no clear association to seropositivity [OR = 1.62, 95% CI 0.23 – 11.19]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)		
	<p>Purchasing males over 1 year of age Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 3.21, 95% CI 1.00 – 10.26]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)		
	<p>Two or more cattle purchase addresses (versus up to 1) associated with higher herd-level presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 3.2, 95% CI 1.4-7.5]</p>	Cattle	Frequent purchase of animals is a risk factor	(van Engelen et al., 2014)		
	<p>Cow origin - PURCHASED (versus homebreed) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.05, 95% CI 1.14-3.68]</p>	Cattle	Animal sourcing outside the farm is a risk factor	(Menadi et al., 2020)		
	<p>Purchasing cattle from abroad Associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 2.68, 95% CI 1.08-6.69]</p>	Cattle	Animal sourcing outside the country is a risk factor	(Boroduske et al., 2017)		
	<p>Adding new animals to the herd associated with higher herd-level seropositivity [OR = 19.9, 95% CI 2.9-137.3]</p>	Cattle	Introducing new animals into herd is a risk factor	(Obaidat & Kersh, 2017)		
						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In cattle, study indicates frequent movement of cattle from the farm is a risk factor (Paul et al., 2014). In small ruminants, 2 studies identified the practice of animal loaning as a risk factor (Lafi et al., 2020; Meadows et al., 2015b).

		Animals are sourced from up to 3 other herds (versus homebred) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.27, 95% CI 1.05-1.53]	Cattle	Sourcing animals from multiple locations is a risk factor	(Nusinovici et al., 2014)	<p>Cleaning, disinfection practices and hygienic measures generally had a protective effect.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In cattle, the use of disinfectants was protective in 2 studies (Menadi et al., 2020; Czaplicki et al., 2012). • In goats, one study identified the use of non-domestically sourced straw for bedding as a risk factor (Schimmer et al., 2011). • In ruminants, frequent cleaning of feeders (Obaidat & Kersh, 2017) had a protective effect. Frequent cleaning of bedding/litter was protective in one study (van Engelen et al., 2014) but was not significant in another (Cantas et al., 2011). Non-specific cleaning/hygiene practices (frequency of cleaning in general, hygiene measures to prevent
		Animals are sourced from 4 or more other herds (versus homebred) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.31, 95% CI 1.65-3.24]	Cattle	Sourcing animals from multiple locations is a risk factor	(Nusinovici et al., 2014)	
		Loaning sheep that return to farm associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 8.14, 95% CI 1.81-36.361]	Sheep	Loaning animals to other farms is a risk factor	(Meadows et al., 2015b)	
		Loaning rams or bucks during breeding season associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 1.52, 95% CI 1.05-5.3]	Goat, sheep	Loaning animals to other farms is a risk factor	(Lafi et al., 2020)	
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Using disinfectants associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.32, 95% CI 0.14-0.72]	Cattle	Disinfection practices are protective	(Menadi et al., 2020)	
		Disinfection of sheds for heifers associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.45, 95% CI 0.21-0.96]	Cattle	Disinfection practices are protective	(Czaplicki et al., 2012)	
		Disinfection of sheds for cows associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.39, 95% CI 0.17-0.91]	Cattle	Disinfection practices are protective	(Czaplicki et al., 2012)	
		Infrequent cleaning of animal feeders (monthly) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 8, 95% CI 1.5-42.4]	Cattle	Frequent cleaning of feeders is protective	(Obaidat & Kersh, 2017)	
		Infrequent cleaning of animal feeders (less often than bi-weekly) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 13.6, 95% CI 3.4-54.6]	Goat, sheep	Frequent cleaning of feeders is protective	(Obaidat & Kersh, 2017)	
		Cleaning bedding in stable: every other day or less (rather than daily or more) Associated with higher herd-level seropositivity [OR = 2.8, 95% CI 1.1-7.1]	Cattle	Frequent (daily) cleaning of bedding is a protective	(van Engelen et al., 2014)	

		<p>Frequent cleaning of litter cleaning (compared to <5 times/year) has no clear association with seropositivity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5-10 times/year [OR = 0.30, 95% CI 0.04-1.00] • >10 times a year [OR = 0.09, 95% CI 0.008-1.023] 	Cattle, goat, sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Cantas et al., 2011)	infection) were inconclusive in 2 studies (Barkallah et al., 2018; Nokhodian et al., 2016).
		<p>Monthly cleaning (compared to no cleaning) Has no clear association to herd-level seropositivity and presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 0.516, 95% CI 0.051-5.252]</p>	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Barkallah et al., 2018)	
		<p>General hygiene measures (not sharing machinery with other farms, having a calving place, changing boot/clothes before contact with animals, using disinfectant foot baths, and washing hands before contact with animals) had no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR = 0.83, 95% CI 0.47-1.48]</p>	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Nokhodian et al., 2016)	
		<p>Origin of straw is abroad or unknown (compared to domestic/no straw) Associated with higher seroprevalence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Herd-level [OR = 5.0, 96% CI 1.3-19.6] • Animal-level [OR = 3.3, 95% CI 1.4-7.9] 	Goat	Unknown origin of bedding/from abroad is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
	Management of feed, supplements and farm equipment	<p>Common watering point associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.3, 95% CI 0.16-0.6]</p>	Sheep	Using common watering points is protective	(Guesmi et al., 2023)	Regarding feed, supplement and equipment management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, protective factors were using common watering points (Guesmi et al., 2023) and use of automatic milking systems (van Engelen et al., 2014) while sharing equipment
<p>Use of automatic milking system associated with lower herd-level presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 0.2, 95% CI 0.1-0.6]</p>	Cattle	Using automatic milking systems is protective	(van Engelen et al., 2014)			

		Sharing equipment (machines) with other herds associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 3.62, 95% CI 1.03-12.76]	Cattle	Sharing equipment with other herds is a risk factor	(Agger et al., 2013)	with other herds was associated with increased seroconversion risk (Agger et al., 2013).
	Visitors/vets/suppliers	Visitor access to kidding does (agrotourism) associated with higher seroprevalence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> animal-level [OR = 2.1, 95% CI 1.3–3.6] operation-level [OR = 22.8, 95% CI 2.4–220.9] 	Goat	Agrotourism with access increases risk	(Welch et al., 2024)	Factors related to agrotourism: In ruminants, animal contact with visitors was associated with increased risk in 2 studies (Welch et al., 2024; Agger et al., 2013). Veterinarians not taking hygienic precautions prior to entering the herd were also identified as risk factors in 2 studies (Agger et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2012), but the effect of using farm boots/outfits as precaution was inconclusive (Schimmer et al., 2014).
		Animal contact with human visitors associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 4.17, 95% CI 1.41-12.5]	Cattle	Animal–visitor contact is a risk factor	(Agger et al., 2013)	
		No hygienic precautions by veterinarian before entering the herd associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 5, 95% CI 1.66-15.12]	Cattle	Veterinarians not following hygienic precautions is a risk factor	(Agger et al., 2013)	
		No hygienic precautions taken by veterinarian associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 8.91, 95% CI 2-22.23]	Cattle	Veterinarians not following hygienic precautions is a risk factor	(Paul et al., 2012)	
		Farm boots and/or outfit as hygiene measures applied for professional farm visitors has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.12, 95% CI 0.96-10.1]	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	
	Pest and rodent control	No traces of vermin in roughage last 12 months associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 5.61, 95% CI 2.01-15.68]	Sheep	Absence of vermin is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	Factors related to pest and rodent control: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In small ruminants, absence/no knowledge of pests in feed was identified as a risk factor in 1 study (Schimmer et al., 2014), but this association was not significant in another (Schimmer et al., 2011).
		Don't know about traces of vermin in roughage last 12 months associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.41, 95% CI 1.48-7.89]	Sheep	No knowledge of vermin presence is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	

		<p>No/Don't know about traces of vermin in roughage last 12 months has no clear association to herd-level seropositivity [OR = 4.3, 95% CI 0.8-22.3]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covering air spaces to control nuisance animals was associated with higher seroprevalence risk (Schimmer et al., 2011).
		<p>Control of nuisance animals (e.g. wild birds) by covering air spaces associated with higher seroprevalence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Herd- level [OR = 48.8, 95% CI 4.0-591.2] • Animal level [OR = 3.7, 95% CI 1.8-7.9] 	Goat	Control of nuisance animals is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
	Artificial insemination	<p>Use of artificial insemination associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.3, 95% CI 1.2-4.7]</p>	Goat	Use of artificial insemination is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	<p>Factors associated to reproduction and parturition management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In goats, the use of artificial insemination was a risk factor in 1 study (Schimmer et al., 2011). • In cattle, artificial insemination by other people than a technician was a risk factor in 1 study (Agger et al., 2013), but the use of AI did not have a conclusive effect (Nokhodian et al., 2016).
		<p>Insemination by other people than artificial insemination technician associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 7.69, 95% CI 2.08-16.95]</p>	Cattle	Artificial insemination by non- trained personnel is a risk factor	(Agger et al., 2013)	
		<p>Use of artificial insemination has no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR = 0.3, 95% CI 0.07-1.21]</p>	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Nokhodian et al., 2016)	
		<p>Use of both artificial and natural insemination has no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR = 0.49, 95% CI 0.06-3.78]</p>	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Nokhodian et al., 2016)	
	Birthing and abortion hygiene protocols	<p>Disinfecting the umbilical cord associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.6, 95% CI 0.4-0.9]</p>	Cattle	Following disinfection protocols during calving is protective	(Carbonero et al., 2015)	<p>Birthing and abortion hygiene protocols:</p> <p>In ruminants, following cleaning/disinfection protocols during birthing was identified as protective in 6 studies (Carbonero et al., 2015; Taurel et al., 2011; Welch et al., 2024; Elsohaby et al., 2021; Meadows et al., 2015b; Meadows et al., 2015a), highlighting practices such as disinfection of umbilical cord, systematic removal of birthing</p>
		<p>Disposing of placenta in manure pile has no clear association to seropositivity [OR = 0.22, 95% CI 0.03-1.85]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
		<p>No lambing pen cleaning practices (changing bedding, remove birthing material, disinfection) Has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 0.97, 95% CI 0.04-23.29]</p>	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015b)	

		No kidding pen hygiene practices Associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 160.97, 95% CI 2.39-10822.2]	Goat	Kidding pen hygiene practices are protective	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	materials and foetus and the changing of bedding. However, the effect was not always significant (Welch et al., 2024; Meadows et al., 2015a; Meadows et al., 2015b).
		No protocol for systematic removal of the foetus and/or placenta of aborted cow associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 2.96, 95% CI 1.11-7.87]	Cattle	Removal of birthing materials is protective	(Taurel et al., 2011)	
		Change bedding after abortion associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.42, 95% CI = 0.23-0.76]	Sheep	Bedding replacement after abortion protective	(Elsohaby et al., 2021)	
		Adding bedding and removing birthing materials WITHOUT disinfection associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 8.96, 95% CI 2.17-36.9]	Sheep	Following disinfection and cleaning protocols during lambing is protective	(Meadows et al., 2015b)	
		Adding bedding WITHOUT removing birthing materials and WITHOUT disinfection associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 5.94, 95% CI 1.1-32.12]	Sheep	Following disinfection and cleaning protocols during lambing is protective	(Meadows et al., 2015b)	
		Adding bedding WITHOUT removing birthing materials and WITHOUT disinfection Has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 4.65, 95% CI 0.26 – 84.11]	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
		Adding bedding and removing birthing materials WITHOUT disinfection Associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 19.3, 95% CI 1.13-330.35]	Goat	Following disinfection and cleaning protocols during kidding is protective	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
	Birthing and abortion hygiene protocols/ separation practices	No cleaning protocol after abortion (placenta/ foetus removal, cleaning/disinfection of kidding, aborting doe <u>separation from other does</u>) Associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 4.0, 95% CI = 2.1-7.4]	Goat	Following disinfection and cleaning protocols during lambing and <u>separation after abortion is protective</u>	(Welch et al., 2024)	
		No cleaning protocol after abortion (placenta/ foetus removal,	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Welch et al., 2024)	

		<p>cleaning/disinfection of kidding, aborting doe separation from other does) Has no clear association with operation-level seropositivity [OR = 9.1, 95% CI 0.9-94.7]</p>				
	<p>Parturition environment and separation practices</p>	<p>Isolation of aborted ewes associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.41, 95% CI = 0.25–0.67]</p>	<p>Sheep</p>	<p>Isolation after abortion is protective</p>	<p>(Elsohaby et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Factors associated with parturition environment and separation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In small ruminants, goats kidding outdoors was protective, but this was identified as a risk factor for kidding outdoors on farms with pigs (Meadows et al., 2015a). For sheep, lambing outdoors had an inconclusive effect (Meadows et al., 2015b). • In ruminants, separating animals for parturition/abortion was protective in 4 studies (Hussain et al., 2022; Welch et al., 2024; Elsohaby et al., 2021; Dabaja et al., 2019), but this effect was not always significant (Welch et al., 2024; Meadows et al., 2015b) and a potential risk factor in 2 studies (Meadows et al., 2015a; Meadows et al., 2015b).
<p>Kidding outdoors in the presence of pig farms associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 29.41, 95% CI 1.26-685.49]</p>		<p>Goat</p>	<p>Kidding outdoors in proximity to pig of pig farms is a factor</p>	<p>(Meadows et al., 2015a)</p>		
<p>Lambing outdoors has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 0.44, 95% CI 0.02-11.01]</p>		<p>Sheep</p>	<p>Association is inconclusive</p>	<p>(Meadows et al., 2015b)</p>		
<p>Kidding outdoors associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.01, 95% CI 0.001 – 0.17]</p>		<p>Goat</p>	<p>Kidding outdoors is protective</p>	<p>(Meadows et al., 2015a)</p>		
<p>No separate parturition area associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence OR = 3.17, 95% CI 1.76-5.86]</p>		<p>Cattle, buffalo</p>	<p>Separate parturition area is protective</p>	<p>(Hussain et al., 2022)</p>		
<p>Lambing pen is present associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.46, 95% CI 0.28–0.76]</p>		<p>Sheep</p>	<p>Separate parturition area is protective</p>	<p>(Elsohaby et al., 2021)</p>		
<p>Separation of lambing ewes from flock (versus lambing in the same airspace)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Always separating: no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 2.08, 95% CI 0.43-10.1] • Sometimes separating: associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence Sometimes separating: [OR = 11.26, 95% CI 2.91-43.56] 		<p>Sheep</p>	<p>Association is inconclusive/ Separating lambing ewes from the flock in a separate airspace is a risk factor</p>	<p>(Meadows et al., 2015b)</p>		
<p>Lambing and kidding at the same areas associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 3.16, 95% CI 1.5-6.4]</p>		<p>Cattle, goat, sheep</p>	<p>Separate parturition area is protective</p>	<p>(Dabaja et al., 2019)</p>		

		Kidding in separate airspace from the rest of herd associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 14.33, 95% CI 1.86 - 110.14]	Goat	Kidding in separate airspace from the flock is a risk factor	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	<p>Factors associated to farm management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In ruminants: contact with other animals (such as cats, dogs, mice, pigeons or wildlife) was associated with increased risk in 6 studies (Barkallah et al., 2018; Robi et al., 2023; Lafi et al., 2020; Turcotte et al., 2021; Schimmer et al., 2011; Mazeri et al., 2013) however this association was not always significant (Cantas et al., 2011; Schimmer et al., 2011; Belhouari et al., 2022). A total of 4 studies indicated contact with other herds was a risk factor (Menadi et al., 2020; Rizzo et al., 2016; Meadows et al., 2015a; Obaidat & Kersh, 2017), and one study indicated a protective effect in goats (Welch et al., 2024) In small ruminants, herds combining multiple species was a risk factor in 1 study (Rizzo et al., 2016) and protective in another (Welch et al., 2024), while contact with pigs was inconclusive (Meadows et al., 2015a). In horses, one study identified contact with small ruminants as a risk factor (Ansel et al., 2020).
	Contact with other animals	Presence of carnivores (cats and dogs) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence and presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 64.05, 95% CI 4.04-1015.57]	Sheep	Presence of carnivores is a risk factor	(Barkallah et al., 2018)	
		Presence of carnivores (dogs and cats) on farm has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 3.33, 95% CI 0.762-1.02]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Cantas et al., 2011)	
		Presence of dogs, cats and mice associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.5, 95% CI 1.21-5.28]	Cattle	Presence of carnivores and rodents is a risk factor	(Robi et al., 2023)	
		Presence of cats on farms associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 1.63, 95% CI 1.21-6.21]	Goat, sheep	Presence of carnivores is a risk factor	(Lafi et al., 2020)	
		Dog on the farm Associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence and pathogen shed [OR = 12.5, 95% CI 1.9 – inf]	Small ruminants	Presence of carnivores is a risk factor	(Turcotte et al., 2021)	
		Presence of dogs in the stable has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.8, 95% CI 1.0-14.2]	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
		Presence of cats in the stable associated with higher seroprevalence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Herd-level [OR = 6.3, 95% CI 1.5-25.8] Animal level [OR = 2.6, 95% CI 1.2-5.6] 	Goat	Presence of carnivores is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
		Accessibility to wild animals (versus no access) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 4.2, 95% CI 1.01-17.18]	Cattle	Contact with wild animals is a risk factor	(Robi et al., 2023)	
		Sporadic presence of pigeons on farms (versus no pigeons) has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Belhouari et al., 2022)	

		[OR = 0.641, 95% CI 0.161-2.552]				
		Daily presence of pigeons on farms (versus no pigeons) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 3.125, 95% CI 1.404-6.955]	Sheep	Contact with birds is a risk factor	(Belhouari et al., 2022)	
		During cattle grazing or transhumance buffaloes are present associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 1.89, 95% CI 1.17-3.05]	Cattle	Contact with other animals/herds is a risk factor	(Mazeri et al., 2013)	
	Contact with other herds	Contact with other herds associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.95, 95% CI 1.12-3.42]	Cattle	Contact with other herds is a risk factor	(Menadi et al., 2020)	
		Contact with other flocks associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 2.1, 95% CI 1.2-3.6]	Goat, sheep	Contact with other flocks is a risk factor	(Rizzo et al., 2016)	
		Presence of other sheep or goat farms within 5km associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 5.59, 95% CI 1.01 – 30.85]	Goat	Proximity to other herds is a risk factor	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
		Mixing animals with animals from another farm Associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 8, 95% CI 2.1-30.8]	Goat, sheep	Contact with other herds is a risk factor	(Obaidat & Kersh, 2017)	
		No contact with other goats on adjacent properties (fence-line contact) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 4.5, 95% CI 1.9–10.9]	Goat	Contact with other herds is protective	(Welch et al., 2024)	
		Herds combining multiple species	No cattle present in operation (versus operations with cattle) associated with higher seroprevalence (OR = 1.8, 95% CI = 1.2-2.6)	Goat	Goat farms with cattle associated with lower seroprevalence	(Welch et al., 2024)
			Mixed flocks rather than farms with only sheep or only goats associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 2.4, 95% CI 1.4-4.2]	Goat, sheep	Contact with other animals is a risk factor	(Rizzo et al., 2016)

		Horse contact with small ruminants associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 15.6, 95% CI 1.87-130.02]	Horse	Contact with other animals is a risk factor	(Ansel et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In cattle, keeping animals tied or in tie-stalls was protective (Czaplicki et al., 2012; Neare et al., 2023) but the effect was not always significant (Neare et al., 2023). • Two studies presented contradictory results, one indicating the protective effect of housing of animals of different ages in the same shed (Czaplicki et al., 2012), while another indicated that group pens can be a risk factor (Turcotte et al., 2021), but the associations were not always conclusive in this study.
		Presence of pigs on farm has no clear association to seropositivity [OR = 3.42, 95% CI 0.56 - 20.68]	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Meadows et al., 2015a)	
	Animal separation	Lactating cows are kept both loose and tied (versus tied only) has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.54, 95% CI 0.28-45.64]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Neare et al., 2023)	
		Lactating cows are kept loose (versus tied) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 5.56, 95% CI 1.17-26.39]	Cattle	Keeping lactating cows tied is protective	(Neare et al., 2023)	
		Animals kept in group pen only have a higher risk of seropositivity, when compared to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kept in tie stall: [OR = 20.6, 95% CI 1.6-267] • Kept mixed: [OR = 34.2, 95% CI 1.9-607] No clear associated when compared to individual pens: [OR = 6.2, 95% CI 0.39-99.2]	Cattle	Housing animals in group pens is a risk factor	(Turcotte et al., 2021)	
		Keeping heifers in tie-stalls is associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence: [OR = 1.49×10^{-8} , 95% CI 5.39×10^{-9}- 4.11×10^{-8}]	Cattle	Keeping heifers in tie-stalls is protective	(Czaplicki et al., 2012)	
		Keeping animals of all age in the same shed associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.4, 95% CI 0.2-0.81]	Cattle	Housing animals of all ages in same shed is protective	(Czaplicki et al., 2012)	
Access to shelter	No stable has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.5, 95% CI 0.14-15.85]	Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In small ruminants, one study (Welch et al., 2024) showed that 	

		<p>Animals kept indoors has no clear association with operation-level seropositivity (compared to kept in outdoor dry lots) [OR = 4.2, 95% CI 0.7-24]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Welch et al., 2024)	<p>indoor housing was a risk factor, but this effect was not significant in others (Welch et al., 2024; Schimmer et al., 2014).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In addition, the use of windbreak curtains and/or windshields was identified as a risk for higher seroprevalence in 2 studies (Schimmer et al., 2014; Schimmer et al., 2011) but the effect was not always conclusive for wind shields (Schimmer et al., 2011).
		<p>Animals kept indoors associated with higher seroprevalence (compared to kept in open range) [OR = 4.7, 95% CI 1.2–19.4]</p>	Goat	Keeping animals indoors is a risk factor	(Welch et al., 2024)	
	Openness of shelters	<p>Use of windbreak curtain and/or windshields in stable associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.52, 95% CI 1.15-5.54]</p>	Sheep	Use of windbreak and/or windshields is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	
		<p>Use of windbreak curtain associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.8, 95% CI 1.2-6.7]</p>	Goat	Use of windbreak curtain is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
		<p>Use of wind shields has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.7, 95% CI 0.7-4.1]</p>	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
	Perimeter control	<p>Grazing more than 5 km away from the farm associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 0.06, 95% CI 0.01-0.4]</p>	Goat, sheep	Allowing free grazing without perimeter control is protective	(Obaidat & Kersh, 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In small ruminants, animals kept on fenced ranges were at greater risk, but the association was inconclusive for animals kept on fenced farms. (Welch et al., 2024). In addition, allowing grazing at further distances from the farm was indicated as protective in 1 study (Obaidat & Kersh, 2017).
		<p>Animals kept on fenced farms has no clear association with seropositivity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Animal-level [OR = 2.8, 95% CI 0.8-10.2] Herd-level [OR = 3.1, 95% CI 0.9-10.3] 	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Welch et al., 2024)	
		<p>Animals kept on fenced ranges associated with higher seroprevalence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> animal-level (compared to open range) [OR = 4.5, 95% CI 1.2-16.3] Herd-level (compared to outdoor dry lots) [OR = 5.0, 95% CI 1.5-16.6] 	Goat	Animals kept on fenced ranges are at greater risk	(Welch et al., 2024)	
	Pasture type	<p>Sheep kept on marginal grounds associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence</p>	Sheep	Marginal ground pastures are a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2014)	<p>In small ruminants, marginal ground pastures were identified as a potential risk factor (Schimmer et al., 2014),</p>

		[OR = 7.04, 95% CI 2.04-24.24]				along with open ranges , however the latter association was not always conclusive (Welch et al., 2024)
		Herds are kept on an open range (versus outdoor dry lot) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 18.6, 95% CI 1.3-265.2]	Goat	Animals kept on open ranges are at greater risk	(Welch et al., 2024)	
		Animals kept on an outdoor dry lot (versus open range) has no clear association with animal-level seropositivity [OR = 1.7, 95% CI 0.5–6.6]	Goat	Association is inconclusive	(Welch et al., 2024)	
	Access to veterinary care	Routine herd health contract with veterinarian associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 4.32, 95% CI 1.51-12.36]	Cattle	Routine veterinary care is a risk factor	(Agger et al., 2013)	In cattle, routine herd health contract with a veterinarian was a risk factor in 1 study (Agger et al., 2013).
	Handling of sick or dead animals	Burial as the primary form of carcass disposal association with lower seropositivity/presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 0.1, 95% CI 0.1-0.2] No clear association with Incineration [OR = 1.4, 95% CI 0.7-2.8] or compost [OR = 1.3, 95% CI 0.8-1.9]	Goat	Only protective form of carcass disposal is burial	(Anderson et al., 2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In goats, 1 study indicates the protective effect of burial of carcasses, whereas other forms of disposal were inconclusive (Anderson et al., 2015). Another risk factor was close proximity to bulk milk-PCR positive farms (Schimmer et al., 2011).
		Less than 8km to nearest bulk milk-PCR positive farm Associated with higher seroprevalence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> herd-level [OR = 12.9, 95% CI 3.0-54.8] animal-level [OR = 3.2, 95% CI 1.4-7.3] 	Goat	Being in proximity to PCR positive farms is a risk factor	(Schimmer et al., 2011)	
Crimean-Congo Haemorrhagic Fever virus	Herds combining multiple species	Keeping cattle in the household has no clear association to seropositivity [OR = 8.96, 95% CI 0.76-106]	Goats	Association is inconclusive	(Lysholm et al., 2022a)	In small ruminants , farm management factors such as closed housing, trough-feeding and presence of rural poultry on the farm were each protective (Kasi

	Herds combining multiple species/contact with other animals	No rural poultry on farm associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 2.93, 95% CI 1.41-6.29]	Goat, sheep	Rural poultry on farm is protective	(Kasi et al., 2020)	et al., 2020). Whereas the effect of keeping mixed-species herds was inconclusive (Lysholm et al., 2022a).
	Openness of shelters	Open housing rather than closed associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 3.76, 95% CI 1.57-9.56]	Goat, sheep	Closed housing is protective	(Kasi et al., 2020)	
	Feed and supplements management	No equipment to feed animals (grazing) (compared to trough-feeding) associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 4.18, 95% CI 1.79-10.39]	Goat, sheep	Trough-feeding is protective	(Kasi et al., 2020)	
Epizootic haemorrhagic disease virus (EHDV)	Quarantine	Purchase of animals without quarantine associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.49, 95% CI 1.83-6.66]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Quarantine protocol is protective	(Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014)	In ruminants , one study indicated the protective effect of quarantine whereas presence of organic waste and muddy soil were risk factors (Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014).
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Presence of organic and other waste on the farm associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.09, 95% CI 1.3-3.42]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Presence of waste on the farm is a risk factor	(Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014)	
	Pasture type	Presence of muddy soil on the farm associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.57, 95% CI 1.06-3.94]	Cattle, goat, sheep	Presence of muddy soil on the farm is a risk factor	(Cetre-Sossah et al., 2014)	
Equine Infectious Anaemia Virus (EIAV)	Management of feed, supplements and farm equipment	Using shared saddle and tacks (versus own) has no clear association with seropositivity [OR not calculated, p = 0.26]	Equines	Association is inconclusive	(Borges et al., 2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In equines, 1 study indicated the protective effect of separating riding equipment (Nogueira et al., 2017), but the effect was not always significant (Borges et al., 2013). In addition, sharing water sources with other farms was identified as a risk factor (Pinho et al., 2025). 2 studies indicate that limiting exposure to sick horses is protective (Nogueira et al., 2017; Machado et al., 2024), alongside
		Separation of riding equipment associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.076, 95% CI 0.008-0.661]	Equines	Separation of riding equipment is protective	(Nogueira et al., 2017)	
		Sharing water sources with other farms associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 1.76, 95% CI 1.26-2.46]	Equines	Sharing water sources with other farms is a risk factor	(Pinho et al., 2025)	
	Disease detection and record-keeping	Testing practice associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.024, 95% CI 0.002-0.28]	Equines	Having a routine testing practice is protective	(Nogueira et al., 2017)	

	Handling of sick or dead animals	Horses on the property come from places or stay together with horses infected with EIA associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 30, 95% CI 3.4-264.5]	Horses	Limiting contact/exposure to sick horses is protective	(Machado et al., 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> with having a routine resting practice (Nogueira et al., 2017). • One study indicated increased risk of seroconversion when using vaccination pistols (de Padua et al., 2022). • Animal sourcing and vaccination against other infections did not show conclusive associations (Barros et al., 2018; Borges et al., 2013).
		Segregation of seropositive animals associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.038, 95% CI 0.004-0.356]	Equines	Limiting contact/exposure to sick horses is protective	(Nogueira et al., 2017)	
	Veterinary Medicine Administration	Use of vaccination pistol associated with higher herd-level seroprevalence [OR = 5.215, 95% CI 1.58-20.142]	Equines	Use of vaccination pistol is a risk factor	(de Padua et al., 2022)	
		Vaccine against other infections has no clear association for with seropositivity [OR = 2.83, 95% CI 0.58-13.82]	Equines	Association is inconclusive	(Borges et al., 2013)	
	Animal sourcing	Origin of equines (purchased) has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.024, 95% CI 1-1.049]	Equines	Association is inconclusive	(Barros et al., 2018)	
Leishmania infantum	Access to shelter	Animal spends the night free, not fastened on a leash associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.33, 95% CI 0.13-0.8]	Dog	Allowing dogs to roam freely at night is protective	(Braz et al., 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In dogs, allowing to roam freely a night was found protective in 1 study (Braz et al., 2021), while daily peridomicile cleaning did not show a conclusive effect (Lopes et al., 2016).
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Daily peridomicile cleaning has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 0.711, 95% CI 0.494-1.021]	Dog	Association is inconclusive	(Lopes et al., 2016)	
Lumpy Skin Disease Virus (LSDV)	Animal sourcing	Replacement cattle are sourced from outside the herd (versus homebred) associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 8.7, 95% CI 2.8-27]	Cattle	Animal sourcing outside the farm is a risk factor	(Kiplagat et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In cattle, animal sourcing from outside the herd was identified as a risk factor in 2 studies (Kiplagat et al., 2020; Susanti et al., 2023), as well as the presence of livestock collectors/traders near the farm (Susanti et al., 2023). • Contact with other animals was identified as a risk factor one study (Selim et al., 2021), but protective in another (Molla et al., 2018), whereas contact with other herds
		Introduction of new livestock associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 4.08, 95% CI 1.27-13.12]	Cattle	Introducing new animals into herd is a risk factor	(Susanti et al., 2023)	
	Handling of sick or dead animals	Symptoms in neighbouring farms associated with higher herd-level presence of pathogen DNA [OR = 5.13, 95% CI 1.72-15.32]	Cattle	Being in proximity to farms with clinical signs is a risk factor	(Huyen et al., 2025)	

	Visitors/vets/suppliers	Presence of livestock collectors/traders near the farm location associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 12.09, 95% CI 3.66-39.91]	Cattle	Presence of livestock collectors/traders near the farm location is a risk factor	(Susanti et al., 2023)	<p>was associated with higher disease incidence (Susanti et al., 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proximity to farms with clinical signs was also shown to have a risk effect (Susanti et al., 2023). • 2 studies indicated increased risk for using communal watering systems (Elsheikh et al., 2024; Selim et al., 2021), and communal feeding systems (Elsheikh et al., 2024). • Another study reported the risk effect of poor management of farm waste (Susanti et al., 2023). • 2 studies indicate the protective effect of indoor housing (Klement et al., 2020; EFSA, 2018a). • Cattle grazing practices showed contradicting associations. Allowing animals to roam freely during grazing was identified as protective (Selim et al., 2021), but another study found grazing associated with higher disease incidence (Sethi et al., 2022). Other grazing practices did not have a conclusive effect (Selim et al., 2021).
	Management of feed, supplements and farm equipment	Communal feeding and watering system rather than separate associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 3.05, 95% CI 1.8-5.14] But has no clear association with animal mortality [OR = 2.29, 95% CI 0.82-6.47]	Cattle	Communal feeding and watering systems are a risk factor for disease incidence (but association with mortality is not significant)	(Elsheikh et al., 2024)	
		Water source is communal rather than separate associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.283, 95% CI 2.11-5.09]	Cattle	Communal water sources are a risk factor	(Selim et al., 2021)	
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	Poor management of farm waste/dirt associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 2.82, 95% CI 1.06-7.45]	Cattle	Poor management of farm waste is a risk factor	(Susanti et al., 2023)	
	Access to shelter	Cattle are kept outdoors (rather than indoors) associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [Hazard Ratio = 5.72, 95% CI 3.13-10.45]	Cattle	Indoor housing is protective	(Klement et al., 2020)	
		Cattle are kept outdoors (rather than indoors) associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [Hazard Ratio = 6.5695, 95% CI 3.64-11.83]	Cattle	Indoor housing is protective	(EFSA, 2018a)	
	Contact with other animals	Contact with other animals associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.401, 95% CI 1.62-7.1]	Cattle	Contact with other animals is a risk factor	(Selim et al., 2021)	
		Contact with other animals associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.41, 95% CI 0.23-0.74]	Cattle	Contact with other animals is protective	(Molla et al., 2018)	
Contact with other herds	Cattles graze with herds from other farms associated with higher herd-level disease incidence [OR = 4.48, 95% CI 2.06-9.75]	Cattle	Contact with other herds is a risk factor	(Susanti et al., 2023)		

	Grazing practices	Communal grazing system (versus separate) has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 1.546, 95% CI 0.91-2.6]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Selim et al., 2021)	
		Grazing system is a mix of communal and separate (versus separate only) has no clear association with seropositivity [OR = 0.749, 95% CI 0.39-1.42]	Cattle	Association is inconclusive	(Selim et al., 2021)	
		Grazing associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 2.04, 95% CI 1.16-3.57]	Cattle	Animal grazing is a risk factor	(Sethi et al., 2022)	
		Animals allowed to roam freely (Free animal movement) associated with lower seroprevalence [OR = 0.356, 95% CI 0.24-0.52]	Cattle	Allowing to freely roam is protective	(Selim et al., 2021)	
Rift Valley Fever Virus (RVFV)	Herds combining multiple species	Presence of sheep in the household has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 3.11, 95% CI 0.78-12.4]	Sheep, goats	Association is inconclusive	(Lysholm et al., 2022b)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ruminants, animal sourcing from outside the herd had a risk effect (Sindato et al., 2015) but the association was not always significant (Lysholm et al., 2022b). • Herds combining multiple species did not have a significant association (Lysholm et al., 2022b).
	Animal sourcing	Buying sheep and goats from traders or at markets has no clear association with herd-level seropositivity [OR = 1.98, 95% CI 0.58-6.74]	Sheep, goats	Association is inconclusive	(Lysholm et al., 2022b)	
		Animal is sourced outside the herd (rather than homebred) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 5.08, 95% CI 2.74-9.44]	Cattle, sheep, goats	Animal sourcing outside the farm is a risk factor	(Sindato et al., 2015)	
Schmallenberg virus (SBV)	Access to shelter	Animals housed only overnight associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [Fixed effects multivariate model coefficient = -0.86, p < 0.001] [Random effects multivariate model coefficient = -0.95, p = 0.005]	Goats, sheep	Access to shelter is protective	(Helmer et al., 2016)	<p>In small ruminants, one study indicated the protective effect of indoor housing (Helmer et al., 2016), while another reported that goat herds with cattle were associated with lower seroprevalence (Kiene et al., 2024).</p>
		Animals housed indoors permanently associated with lower herd-level seroprevalence [Fixed effects multivariate model coefficient = -1.66, p < 0.001]	Goats, sheep	Access to shelter is protective	(Helmer et al., 2016)	

		[Random effects multivariate model coefficient = -2.09, p < 0.001]				
	Herds combining multiple species	No cattle on farm associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.874, 95% CI 1.249-2.884)	Goat	Presence of cattle on goat farms is protective	(Kiene et al., 2024)	
Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV)	Access to shelter	Horses spend more than 12 hours per day outside has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020-2022 [OR = 0.794, 95% CI 0.368-1716] 2022 [OR = 1729, 95% CI 0.588-5085] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	The SLR identified only one study fitting the biosecurity category for TBEV (Gothe et al., 2023), with access to shelter not significantly associated to seropositivity in horses .
		Horses are permanently outdoor (versus housed less than 12h per day) has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020-2022 [OR = 0.985, 95% CI 0.516-1881] 2022 [OR = 1908, 95% CI 0.726-5012] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	
		Presence of outdoor shelter has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020-2022 [OR = 1568, 95% CI 0.917-2681] 2022 [OR = 1283, 95% CI 0.695-2370] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	
Trypanosoma evansi (Surra)	Disease detection and record-keeping	Positive history of venereal disease associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 9.19, 95% CI 0.9-93.62]	Equids	Association is inconclusive	(Shorba et al., 2024)	In equids, promiscuity with dromedaries had a risk effect (Benfodil et al., 2019), whereas positive history of venereal disease did not show a conclusive association (Shorna et al., 2024).
	Contact with other animals	Promiscuity with dromedaries associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.49, 95% CI 1.23-5.25]	Horse	Contact with other animals is a risk factor	(Benfodil et al., 2019)	
Trypanosoma vivax	Contact with other herds	Presence of alien migratory cattle associated with lower disease incidence [OR = 0.7, 95% CI 0.62-0.77]	Zebu (Bos indicus)	Presence of other cattle migrating along the cattle routes is protective	(Majekodu nmi et al., 2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In zebu, one study identified herd migration during wet and dry seasons as a risk factor, whereas

	Grazing practices	<p>Cattle migration associated with higher disease incidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> During dry season: [OR = 1.22, 95% CI 1.01-1.37] During wet season: [OR = 1.23, 95% CI 1.03-1.47] 	Zebu (Bos indicus)	Cattle migration during both wet and dry seasons are potential risk factors	(Majekodunmi et al., 2013)	<p>contact with other herds was associated with lower disease incidence (Majekodunmi et al., 2013).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In cattle, recent animal purchases and administration of oxytocin using the same syringe and needle were identified as risk factors in one study (Bastos et al., 2020), and cattle tethering in communal areas in another (Tegegn et al., 2021). An experimental field study (Leal et al., 2025) assessed the effectiveness of iodine-based glove disinfection for rectal palpation. It found that inadequate disinfection (concentrations up to 0.5%) did not prevent infection in cattle, whereas a 1% iodine solution was 100% effective.
	Animal sourcing	Animal purchased in the last 90 days associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 2.6, 95% CI 2.01-3.37]	Cattle	Purchased animals are a risk factor	(Bastos et al., 2020)	
	Cleaning and disinfection practices and hygienic measures	<p>Reusing the same glove for rectal palpation with insufficient disinfection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disinfection with water: Up to 70% of animals become infected (n = 10) 0.5 % iodine solution: 70-80% iodine effectiveness (n = 20) 	Cattle	Reusing the same glove with insufficient disinfection is a risk factor	(Leal et al., 2025)	
		<p>Disinfecting the glove for rectal palpation with 1% iodine solution was found to have 100% effectiveness in the field (n = 20)</p>	Cattle	Disinfecting rectal palpation gloves with stronger concentrations is protective	(Leal et al., 2025)	
	Perimeter control	Tethering cattle rather than communal grazing (in tsetse suppression area) associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 2.07, 95% CI 1.06-3.92]	Cattle	Cattle tethering in vector-controlled areas is a risk factor	(Tegegn et al., 2021)	
	Veterinary Medicine Administration	Use of exogenous oxytocin during milking sharing the same syringe and needle associated with higher disease incidence [OR = 18.42, 95% CI 12.32-27.54]	Cattle	Administration of oxytocin using the same syringe and needle is a risk factor	(Bastos et al., 2020)	
Vesicular Stomatitis virus (VSV)	Grazing practices	Animals have access to pasture associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 8.1, 95% CI 2-32.2]	Horse	Access to pasture is a risk factor	(Urie et al., 2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In equines, contact with sick horses (Urie et al., 2018), and access to pasture (Hurd et al., 1999; Urie et al., 2018) were identified as risk factors, whereas access to shelter was protective (Hurd et al., 1999). In ruminants, access to shelter and access to pasture were not
		Animals have access to pasture associated with higher risk of herd-level disease incidence [OR = 2.01, 95% CI 1.07-3.71]	Equines	Access to pasture is a risk factor for equines only	(Hurd et al., 1999)	
		Animals have access to pasture has no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR = 2.7, 95% CI 0.2-157.3]	Cattle, Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Hurd et al., 1999)	

	Access to shelter	Access to shelter has no clear association with herd-level disease incidence [OR = 1.2, 95% CI 0.3-5.5]	Cattle, Sheep	Association is inconclusive	(Hurd et al., 1999)	significantly associated to disease incidence (Hurd et al., 1999).
		Access to shelter associated with lower herd-level disease incidence [OR = 0.5, 95% CI 0.3-0.9]	Equines	Access to shelter is protective for equines only	(Hurd et al., 1999)	
	Handling of sick or dead animals	Contact with clinical case horses associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 17.6, 95% CI 1.8-171.2]	Horse	Contact with infected or exposed animals is a risk factor	(Urie et al., 2018)	
West Nile Fever Virus (WNV)	Travel history	Transport with a distance of more than 20 km from the holding within the last year has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020-2022 [OR = 1.887, 95% CI 0.917-3882] 2022 [OR = 1.43, 95% CI 0.66-3101] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In equines, recent travel history was associated with higher seroprevalence (Garcia-Bocanegra et al., 2012), however the effect was not always significant (Gothe et al., 2023). Access to shelter was identified to have a protective effect (Chevalier et al., 2025; Pradel et al., 2009), whereas another study indicated that spending more time outdoors is associated with lower seroprevalence (Gothe et al., 2023), although the association was not always conclusive. The use of fans in the stable was associated with higher seroprevalence (Rios et al., 2009), while the use of fly sheets did not have a conclusive effect (Gothe et al., 2023). The Gothe et al. (2023) study also investigated the different pasture type association with seropositivity and indicated the potential protective effect of dry-lots, however the effect was not always conclusive.
		Travel outside of Germany Has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2020-2022 [OR = 0.702, 95% CI 0.021-1765] 2022 [OR = 0.327, 95% CI 0.036-2974] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	
		Transport of the horse within the last six months Associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.68, 95% CI 1.84-6.06]	Horse	Recent history of travel is a risk factor	(Garcia-Bocanegra et al., 2012)	
	Access to shelter	Animals kept exclusively on pasture without shelter Associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 3.64, 95% CI 1.11-17.47]	Horse	Access to shelter is protective	(Chevalier et al., 2025)	
		Horses are permanently outdoor (versus outdoors less than 12h per day) associated with lower seroprevalence during 2020-2022 [OR = 0.218, 95% CI 0.059-0.803] But not in 2022 [OR = 0.349, 95% CI 0.093-1309]	Horse	Association is inconclusive / Spending more time outdoors is protective	(Gothe et al., 2023)	

		<p>Horses spend more than 12 hours per day outside (versus outdoors less than 12h per day) associated with lower with seroprevalence during: 2020-2022 [OR = 0.192, 95% CI 0.04-0.921] but not in 2022 [OR = 0.341, 95% CI 0.073-1587]</p>	Horse	Association is inconclusive/ Spending more time outdoors is protective	(Gothe et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close proximity to wildlife parks was indicated as a risk factor (Chevalier et al., 2025). • Lastly, one study reported the risk effect of presence of dead birds and presence of other ill animals (Rios et al., 2009).
		<p>Presence of outdoor shelter has no clear association with seropositivity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020-2022 [OR = 2.319, 95% CI 0.809-6644] • 2022 [OR = 2.424, 95% CI 0.828-7.101] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	
		<p>Animals are kept outside after dusk (rather than in a stable) associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 6, 95% CI 2.2-16.3]</p>	Equines	Access to shelter after dusk is protective	(Pradel et al., 2009)	
	Contact with other animals	<p>Horses are housed further away from the special protected area (SPA) with wild birds (versus 1km closer to SPA) associated with lower risk for seropositivity [OR = 0.93, 95% CI 0.87-0.99]</p>	Horse	Closer distance to wildlife parks is a risk factor	((Chevalier et al., 2025)	
	Equipment and structural measures/ Openness of shelters	<p>Using fly sheets Has no clear association with seropositivity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020-2022 [OR = 0.709, 95% CI 0.249-2-025] • 2022 [OR = 1.111, 95% CI 0.385-3208] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)	
		<p>Use of fans in the stable associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.79, 95% CI 1.22-2.53]</p>	Horse	Use of fans in the stable is a risk factor	(Rios et al., 2009)	
	Pasture type	<p>Type of turnout: Dry lot (versus combination) associated with lower seropositivity: during 2020-2022 [OR = 0.747, 95% CI 0.327-0.921] But not in 2022 [OR = 0.59, 95% CI 0.229-1519]</p>	Horse	Association is inconclusive/ Dry lot turnout is protective	(Gothe et al., 2023)	

		Type of turnout: Pasture (versus combination) has no clear association with seropositivity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020-2022 [OR = 0.558, 95% CI 1.165-1887] • 2022 [OR = 0.438, 95% CI 0.108-1775] 	Horse	Association is inconclusive	(Gothe et al., 2023)
	Handling of sick or dead animals	Presence of dead birds associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 1.97, 95% CI 1.27-3.47]	Horse	Contact with dead birds is a risk factor	(Rios et al., 2009)
		Presence of other ill animals associated with higher seroprevalence [OR = 2.42, 95% CI 1.01-5.79]	Horse	Contact with infected or exposed animals is a risk factor	(Rios et al., 2009)

Annex IV – Systematic literature review culling results

Pathogen	Target species	[Culling measure type] study context/methodology/limitations	Described effect (effectiveness described in terms of morbidity/mortality reduction or other metrics)	Reference(s)	Summary
African horse sickness virus (AHSV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)			
Akabane virus (AKAV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)			
Bluetongue virus (BTV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)			
Bovine ephemeral fever virus (BEFV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)			
<i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i> (<i>B. besnoiti</i>)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)			

Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus (CCHFV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Cache Valley virus (CVV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Eastern/Western equine encephalitis virus (EEEV/WEEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Epizootic hemorrhagic disease virus (EHDV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Equine Infectious anemia virus (EIAV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Schmallenberg virus (SBV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Shuni virus (SHUV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
St. Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
<i>Trypanosoma evansi</i> (T. evansi)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
<i>Trypanosoma vivax</i> (T. vivax)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		

Vesicular stomatitis virus (VSAV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
West Nile virus (WNV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i>	Deer	[Relaxed hunting regulations, poaching, professional sharpshooting] Field study Removal of deer over 28-month period, compared to site without measures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Counts of infected ticks continued to rise (75% at peak) one year after removing 50% reduction in deer population. After all deer removed, infection rates dropped to < 30% Significant negative correlation with tick abundance after culling all deer ($p = 0.04$) In reference site tick abundance continued to rise 	(Rand et al., 2004)	No definitive evidence of efficacy of culling as a risk mitigation measure with only limited data available showing diverging associations between deer densities and Lyme incidence in humans (Rand et al., 2004; Jordan et al., 2007; Kilpatrick et al., 2014).
	Deer	[Relaxed hunting regulations, extension of the hunting season] Field study Association between deer density and human Lyme disease incidence and tick abundance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No clear trend in Lyme incidence rate during the study period Association between deer density and tick abundance or Lyme incidence was not significant ($r^2 = 0.39$, $p = 0.09$) 	(Jordan et al., 2007)	
	Deer	[Controlled archery and shotgun hunting] Field study Association between deer density and human Lyme disease cases and tick abundance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of reported Lyme disease cases per 100 households correlated to deer density ($r^2 = 0.97$, $p > 0.001$) Reducing deer population by 87% resulted in 50% reduction in tick infection rate and 80% reduction in reported Lyme disease cases. 	(Kilpatrick et al., 2014)	
<i>Leishmania infantum (L. infantum)</i>	Dogs	[Euthanasia of seropositive animals] Field study	No significant difference after culling between CanL seroprevalence in 2013 (8.3%) and 2017 (7.8%) ($p=0.764$).	(Vaz et al., 2020)	Evidence is contradictory, some studies support culling seropositive dogs (Zhi-Biao et al., 1989; Werneck et al., 2014; Franca-Silva et al., 2023), others suggest culling alone is insufficient to eradicate CVL in the long term (Vaz et al., 2020; Grimaldi et al., 2012; da Rocha et al., 2018). One modelling study (Seva et al., 2017) indicated culling of rabbits and hares is more effective than dog-focused measures (vaccination and collars). Effectiveness is often reported in terms of reduced human leishmaniasis incidence.
	Dogs	[Euthanasia of seropositive animals] Field study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The culling only temporarily affected cumulative incidence (from 31% to 14% at 10m and 40% at 15m; $p=0.001$) and was insufficient to eradicate CanL. The culling led to a 62% reduction of the canine disease burden during the study period. 	(Grimaldi et al., 2012)	
	Dogs	[Mass elimination of reservoir hosts] Epidemiological report of endemic regions in China	Since implementation of mass elimination of dogs and widespread spraying of insecticides during sandfly season, human visceral-leishmaniasis cases in endemic areas decreased.	(Zhi-Biao, 1989)	

	Dogs	[Elimination of seropositive animals, Elimination + insecticide spraying] Randomized controlled field study in Brazil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infection prevalence: no statistically significant difference in intervention group versus control ($p > 0.2$) • 18-month cumulative infection incidence: lower in culling or culling + spraying groups than control ($p < 0.033$) • Culling effect might be biased due to selective loss to follow-up 	(Werneck et al., 2014)	
	Hares	Modelling study of control measures during a leishmaniasis outbreak in Southwest Madrid. [Euthanasia of hares and/or rabbits] Model parameters estimated to represent 2011 outbreak in Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assuming 50% reproductive rate, culling 75% of rabbits and hares was the most effective strategy in reducing infection across all host species but this level of culling may not be feasible in practice. • Culling only hares had better results than culling only rabbits • Other measures (insecticide impregnated collars and vaccination for dogs) had limited impact. 	(Seva et al., 2017)	
	Dogs	[Euthanasia of seropositive animals + insecticide spraying] Cohort field study, effectiveness measured by reduction in human disease cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No significant differences were seen between three areas under different times of intervention start. • Multivariate analysis indicates control strategies were ineffective in reducing incidence rates 	(da Rocha et al., 2018)	
	Dogs	[Euthanasia of seropositive animals] Cohort field study	Culling significantly reduced CVL prevalence, and human cases decreased by 75% suggesting culling and screening is effective when implemented quickly in endemic areas.	(Franca-Silva et al., 2023)	
<i>Coxiella burnetii</i> (C. burnetii)	Cattle	[Routine culling of shedder cows if presenting clinical signs] Culling applied in tandem with 2-year vaccination program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 44% culling rate in herd over 2 years (128/289 cows) • Only 1.2% of animals shedding by the end of the study. • Not possible to differentiate the effects of vaccination vs. culling, 	(Piñero et al., 2014)	Field studies often report on culling as a secondary measure to vaccination making it difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of culling alone (Piñero et al., 2014; Van den Brom et al., 2015).
	Goat	[Culling of all pregnant animals if farm BTM PCR-positive] Culling applied in tandem with mandatory vaccination program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased risk of becoming BTM-PCR positive on farms where animals were culled (compared to non-infected farms) [OR = 211.7, 95% CI 77.9-576.2, $p > 0.01$] • Multiple years of vaccination associated with reduced risk of BTM-PCR positivity [OR = 0.3 - 0.01, $p < 0.001$] 	(Van den Brom et al., 2015)	One modelling study (Bontje et al., 2016) indicates that culling can reduce abortion strims and number of infected but is insufficient to eradicate the disease in the long term.

	Goat	<p>Modelling study of different control measures</p> <p>Relevant scenarios for culling:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Culling of lactating animals if farm BTM PCR-positive 2. Culling of pregnant goats after abortion storms <p>Epidemiological parameters estimated from abortion patterns in Dutch dairy goat herds 2006-2007</p>	<p>Compared to no control measures: r of infected placentas/year and abortions. Does not</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culling after abortion storms reduces number of infected placentas/year and abortions. Does not eradicate disease from herd within 10 years • Preventive vaccination the most effective measure. Eradicates disease. 	(Bontje et al., 2016)	
Lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV)	Cattle	<p>Modeling study of different control measures</p> <p>Relevant scenarios for culling:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Partial stamping out if clinical cases 2. Total stamping out of affected herds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccination has a greater impact on reducing LSDV spread than culling. If 95% of farms vaccinate with 75% effectiveness, total and partial culling achieve similar chances of eradication. • Without vaccination or with low vaccine effectiveness (e.g., 40%), total culling is more effective than partial. <p><u>Conclusion:</u> Overall, partial culling only slightly increases the number of affected farms compared to total culling.</p>	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2016)	A modelling study (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2016) indicated that vaccination is more effective than culling in controlling infection. Nevertheless, under low effectiveness / no vaccination scenarios, total stamping out is more effective than partial stamping out.
Rift Valley fever virus (RVF)	Cattle, sheep, goats	<p>Modeling study of different control measures</p> <p>Relevant scenarios for culling:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Test and cull 2. Stamping out of infected farms <p>Mayotte models based on real disease incidence data.</p> <p>Netherlands model parameters estimated from epidemics reported in Africa because transmission data not available.</p>	<p>For Mayotte, test and cull strategy has no impact on the number of infected animals nor on epidemic duration, unless 2000 animals tested/day. When considered in combination with vector control (vector reductions of $\geq 40\%$) the efficacy of the culling strategy is increased.</p> <p>For the Netherlands, stamping out of farms in a 20-km radius around detected farms appears as the most effective measure to control RVF spread after introduction in the Netherlands.</p> <p>Culling of only detected farms was less effective.</p>	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2020)	according to a modelled results from EFSA's scientific opinion on Rift Valley fever (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2020) culling animals on farms within a 20 km radius of detected cases was identified as the most effective measure for controlling RVF spread but would involve the culling of a large number of animals

Annex V – Systematic literature review movement restriction results

Pathogen	Target species	[RMM subtype] study context methodology/limitations	Described effect	Reference(s)	Summary
Akabane virus (AKAV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> (<i>B. burgdorferi</i>)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Bovine ephemeral fever virus (BEFV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
<i>Besnoitia besnoitia</i>			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
<i>Leishmania infantum</i> (<i>L. infantum</i>)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus (CCHFV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Cache Valley virus (CVV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Eastern/Western equine encephalitis virus (EEEV/WEEV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		
Epizootic haemorrhagic disease virus (EHDV)			No eligible papers found (SLR=0)		

Equine infectious anaemia virus (EIAV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
Shuni virus (SHUV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
St. Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
Tickborn encephalitis virus (TBEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
<i>Trypanosoma evansi</i> (<i>T. evansi</i>)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
<i>Trypanosoma vivax</i> (<i>T. vivax</i>)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
Vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
West Nile virus (WNV)	No eligible papers found (SLR=0)				
African horse sickness virus (AHSV)	Equines	<p>[Protection zone] Model. Due to limited data, transmission probability and kernels were estimated from BTV8 epidemic in the EU.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The probability of transmission beyond 100 and 150 km is very similar (between 0.1 and 3% beyond 100 km, and between 0.1 and 2% beyond 150 km). A distance of 100 km would capture at least 95% of the risk of spread from the PZ (97-99.9%), while a smaller PZ (e.g. 50 km) would capture at least 90% of the risk of spread (90-99.9%). 	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2021)	Modelling study results from 2 papers (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2021; de Vos et al., 2012) show protection zones and quarantine procedures are

	Equines	[Quarantine, international importation] Stochastic risk model for AHSV spread in the Netherlands due to international equine movements. Integrate historical data from South Africa and Spain.	<p>[Quarantine]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 40-day quarantine, serological test, clinical inspection reduce the annual introduction risk by 46% compared to no measures. Without preventive measures introduction risk would increase by 86%. A 60-day quarantine period (instead of 40 days) would reduce introduction risk by 11%. [International importation] A two-fold increase in horse importations would increase introduction risk by 6%. A 10-fold increase in donkey importations would increase risk by 67%. 	(de Vos et al., 2012)	associated with reduced transmission risk.
Bluetongue virus (BTV)	Cattle, sheep, goats	[Protection zone] Stochastic transmission model using historical movement and temperature data, validated against observed 2007 BTV outbreak data in UK.	<p>Comparison of 3 movement-restriction strategies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3 zone policy: trade ban between farms in innermost control zone (20km); protection zone (100km); surveillance zone (150km) 3 zone policy: movement allowed in innermost control zone (20km); protection zone (100km); surveillance zone (150km) 2 zone policy: radii optimised based on location, movement allowed in control and protection zones <p>Strategy (a) provided the best epidemiological control but at high economic cost. Strategy (b) which permitted movement within the control zone led to greater disease spread and higher costs. Strategy (c) allowed movement and used only two zones with much smaller radii, allowing containment while reducing costs by up to an order of magnitude.</p> <p>Conclusion: strict 3-zone policy is effective in containing spread, but radii can be optimised to achieve similar results in a 2-zone policy with smaller economic impact.</p>	(Spooner et al., 2020)	All studies evaluated were modelling studies, and the evidence is not unanimous. In five modelling papers (Spooner et al., 2020; Turner et al., 2019; Ensoy et al., 2013; Turner et al., 2012; de Koeijer et al., 2011), movement restrictions were shown to be highly effective at reducing BTV spread, with 20 km control zones largely as effective as imposing larger zones. However, one study (Tildesley et al., 2019) concluded that “the cost of any movement ban is greater than the epidemiological benefits due to the low within-farm prevalence and slow rate of disease spread”. Economic losses were also highlighted by Velthuis et al., (2010), whereas another study (Spooner et al., 2020) indicated that movement restriction zone radii could be optimised to reduce economic costs.
	Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Stochastic spatial transmission model using 2007 BTV outbreak data in UK.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Movement restrictions were highly effective at reducing spread, reducing mean distance between infected farm and first index case from 180 km to 115 km. FMD restrictions, in place before BTV detection, further limited spread to 15 km and contributed to containing the infection in the southeast of England. 	(Turner et al., 2019)	
	Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Stochastic spatial mechanistic model using historical BTV data in UK. Economic parameters based on government agency assessments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost of any movement ban is greater than the epidemiological benefits due to the low within-farm prevalence and slow rate of disease spread. Optimal strategy is to not have a complete ban, and allowing free movement of livestock is economically preferable. Movement bans were found to have a limited impact on controlling farm-to-farm spread. 	((Tildesley et al., 2019)	

Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Bayesian transmission model using 2007 BTV outbreak data in UK.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If vector dispersal is primarily local (diffusion model, 99% transmission <25 km), movement restrictions are effective (optimal Movement Restriction Zone ~20 km). If dispersal occurs frequently over longer distances (kernel models, 99% transmission <50 km), movement restrictions are not effective. Vector dispersal accounts for 86-91% of infected farms, while cattle movement accounts for 5-7%. Mean number of secondary infections per infected farm for cattle movement was 0.04 (0.01-0.12)(diffusion model) and 0.06(0.02-0.15) (kernel models). For sheep, movement accounts for 3-6%. Mean number of secondary infections per infected farm for sheep movement was 0.04 (0.01-0.13)(diffusion model) and 0.05(0.02-0.13) (kernel models). 	(Sumner et al., 2017)	Two modelling studies showed that the effect is dependent on the pattern of transmission, which depends on vector dispersal (Szmaragd et al., 2009; Sumner et al., 2017). Movement restrictions are effective in reducing disease incidence if vector dispersal is primarily local.
Cattle	[Protection zone] Transmission model using 2006 BTV outbreak data in Belgium.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Movement restrictions significantly reduced the predicted final size of the outbreak from 582 farms to 295 farms (90% CI = 262-330). Without restriction: 480 farms (95% CI= 387-810). A 15 km restriction zone was as effective as a total ban and increasing radius does not decrease outbreak size. For policies allowing movement in the innermost zone, a 10 km radius is sufficient with larger zones increasing outbreak size. 	(Ensoy et al., 2013)	
Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Stochastic transmission model using 2007 BTV outbreak data in UK. Simultaneous foot and mouth disease outbreak with movement restrictions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Movement restrictions are effective at reducing outbreak size; a 20km control zone is as effective as imposing larger zones. A targeted ban is as effective as a total ban on animal movements. Infection generally cannot be maintained without between-herd vector transmission. Degree of mixing at market has virtually no effect on final size. 	(Turner et al., 2012)	
Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Spatio-temporal transmission kernel model based on 2006 BTV outbreak data in Western Europe countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 85% of all transmission takes place within 20km (Protection zone). Animal transport restrictions can slow down the spatial spread of BTV-8 substantially. 	(de Koeijer et al., 2011)	
Cattle, sheep, goats	[Protection zone] Deterministic economic model for the 2006-2007 BTV-8 epidemic in the Netherlands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The model reconstructed the dynamics of spread in 20km zone (most restrictions) and 100km zone (less restrictions). Within a few months after the first outbreak, more than 50% of farms were placed in the 20km zones, reaching 100% of farms in one year. Movement restrictions were the single largest contributor to the economic impact of the outbreak. 	(Velthuis et al., 2010)	
Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Stochastic transmission kernel model based on 2007 BTV outbreak data in UK.	Results for a Gaussian kernel (best fit) suggest that movement restrictions in the protection zone have little impact on spread and are not necessary.	(Szmaragd et al., 2009)	

		Uncertainty in kernel shapes; the results depend on the kernel used.	Results using a kernel from the 2001 foot and mouth disease outbreak suggest movement restrictions are effective at reducing spread.		
<i>Coxiella burnetii</i> (C. burnetii)	Cattle	[Trade control] Model assessing contributions of airborne transmission and trade using observed seroprevalence data in 2012 in France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8% new herd infections were attributed to cattle trade. Airborne transmission caused relatively small and short intra-herd outbreaks, while cattle trade led to larger outbreaks. Herds infected by cattle trade had higher probability of infection and lower extinction rates compared to airborne infected herds. 	(Pandit et al., 2016)	One modelling study (Pandit et al., 2016) fit to outbreak data from France concluded that movement restrictions (trade control) can help but are insufficient on their own to prevent the spread of <i>C. burnetii</i> due to the significant role of airborne transmission.
Lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV)	Cattle	[Protection zone] Modeling study Fat tailed- transmission kernel model based on epidemics in Israel and Albania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20km protection zone results in 0.3% (Israel) and 0.2% (Albania) probability of transmission beyond the zone. Beyond a surveillance zone of 50km, probability of transmission is < 0.1%. Smaller radius can still provide high level of protection: 10.3km probability of escape is 1%, and 4.5km probability of escape is 5%. Considering model results, current protection and surveillance zones of 20 and 50km defined in the legislation are effective to restrain 95% probability of spread. 	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2022a)	An EFSA scientific opinion modelled movement control effectiveness (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2022a), with the results indicating that protection and movement control zones greatly limit the spread of LSDV.
Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV)	Cattle	[Trade control] Hybrid spatiotemporal compartmental model validated against historical RVF outbreaks in East Africa	Movement restrictions are most effective when transmissibility is high and geographic spread is greatest.	(McMahon et al., 2014)	Three modelling studies (McMahon et al., 2014; EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2022b; EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2020) concluded that movement restrictions are mostly effective. Protection zones of 20 km and 50 km radii are recommended to contain RVFV transmission. However, one modelling study (Tennant et al., 2021) suggested that restricting livestock exports and imports only delayed an outbreak to a season more suitable for transmission, resulting in a more severe outbreak.
	Cattle, sheep, goats	[Protection zone] Model of RVFV spread in Europe Kernels estimated from outbreaks in Tanzania in 2007 or based on reported dispersal distances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The estimated probability of RVF transmission beyond a protection zone with 20 km radius, if transmission occurred, is 5.7% (CI: 0.7-23.2%), and 0.1% (0.1-2.6%) for a zone with 50 km radius. The size of the protection and surveillance zones for RVF of 20 and 50 km is recommended as sufficient to contain disease transmission with at least 95% probability. 	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2022b)	
	Cattle, sheep, goats	[Protection zone] Bayesian metapopulation model based RVF serological data from 2004-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restricting livestock exports/imports only served to delay an outbreak to a season which was more suitable for transmission in most simulations, resulting in a more severe outbreak. <5% of movement-restriction control simulations caused a decrease to the total number of infections, suggesting that there may be effective movement-restriction scenarios. 	(Tennant et al., 2021)	
	Cattle, sheep, goats	[Protection zone] Stochastic transmission age-stratified model of spread in Mayotte (France) and the Netherlands	RVFV would spread beyond a radius of up to 100 km or 50 km from the infected area with 10% or 55% probability, respectively.	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2020)	

		Kernels estimated from outbreaks in Tanzania in 2007 or based on reported dispersal distances			
Schmallenberg virus (SBV)	Cattle, sheep	[Protection zone] Kernel and diffusion transmission models using 2011 SBV seroprevalence data from Belgium and Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Movement restrictions can potentially reduce outbreak size. Cattle movement accounts for 1% of infected farms (while vector dispersal accounts for 98%). • But depends critically on vector dispersal assumptions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If vector dispersal is primarily local, movement restrictions have a substantial impact. - If dispersal occurs frequently over longer distances, movement restrictions have no impact. 	(Sumner et al., 2017)	One modelling study (Sumner et al., 2017) concluded, as also observed for BTV, that the impact of restricting livestock movements on the spread SBV depends critically on assumptions made about the distances over which vector dispersal occurs. If vector dispersal is primarily local, movement restrictions have a substantial impact

Annex VI - Systematic literature review vaccination results

Pathogen	Target species	Study type (Country)	Trade name [vaccine type]	Measured Clinical Endpoint	Reported effectiveness (quantitative)	Described effect	Reference	SUMMARY
Akabane virus (AKAV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
<i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i>		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus (CCHV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Cache Valley virus (CCV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Epizootic haemorrhagic disease virus (EHDV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Vesicular stomatitis virus (VSAV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Schmallenberg virus (SBV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Shuni virus (SHUV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
St. Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
Tickborne encephalitis virus (TBEV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
<i>Trypanosoma evansi</i> (T. evansi)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						

Pathogen	Target species	Study type (Country)	Trade name [vaccine type]	Measured Clinical Endpoint	Reported effectiveness (quantitative)	Described effect	Reference	SUMMARY
Western equine encephalitis virus (WEEV)		No eligible papers found (SLR=0)						
African horse sickness virus (AHSV)	Horses	Outbreak (South Africa)	Trade name not specified [Live attenuated polyvalent]	Mortality / Fatal Disease	Unvaccinated animals (vs. annual vaccination) [OR = 8.7, 95% CI = 4-19.2]	Annual vaccination associated with higher survival rates	(Genis et al., 2023)	In field studies, vaccination was associated with higher survival rates, lower disease risk and incidence and effective in controlling disease spread.
	Horses	AHSV-1 outbreak (South Africa)	Trade name not specified [Modified live attenuated serotype 1]	Pathogen Detection (Viral Shedding)	Vaccination status negatively associated with infection ($p = 0.04$) in the epicentre	Vaccination was significantly associated with reduced infection risk in the epicentre	(Grewar et al., 2019)	
	Horses	AHSV-2 outbreak (Senegal)	Trade name not specified [Live attenuated, 7-8 strains included]	Mortality / Fatal Disease	Correlation between number of vaccinated horses and disease incidence in 3 regions [Fatick -0.34; Thies -0.60; Diourbel -0.61]	After the mass vaccination was started, a decrease of the disease incidence in three severely affected regions in Senegal.	(Diouf et al., 2013)	
	Horses	Cross-sectional field study (Zimbabwe)	Trade name not specified [Live attenuated polyvalent]	Mortality / Fatal Disease	Vaccinated horses (vs. unvaccinated) [OR = 0.12, 95% CI = 0.044-0.35]	Vaccinated horses had significantly lower odds of dying from AHS compared with unvaccinated horses	(Gordon et al., 2013)	
	Equines	AHSV-4 outbreak (Portugal)	Trade name not specified [AHS serotype 4 vaccine from World Reference Laboratory at Onderstepoort]	Clinical Illness	NA	The national vaccination campaign achieved 100% coverage of the Portuguese equine population. One year after the campaign, no further cases were reported. NOTE: Movement restrictions and stamping out did not stop the early spread of AHSV, and cases continued to occur despite these control measures.	(Portas et al., 1999)	
Bluetongue virus (BTV)	Cattle, sheep	Modelling study based	Bovilis BTV8	Pathogen Detection	NA	Using a stochastic spatial model for the spread of BTV in Great Britain	(Gubbins et. al., 2012)	In field and modeling studies, vaccination

		on controlled vaccine trial results (UK)	[inactivated (dead)], authorized in the EU (withdrawn)]	(Pathogen Shedding)		(GB), vaccination was predicted to reduce both the incidence of disease and spatial spread, in both reactive vaccination strategies and when an incursion occurred into a previously vaccinated population.		reduced mortality and morbidity, while effectively slowing the velocity and extent of outbreak spread. While its impact on test positivity (seroprevalence) varies across studies - ranging from significant reductions to no detectable difference - higher vaccine coverage and pre-emptive application are strongly associated with a lower probability of outbreaks and reduced disease incidence.
	Sheep	Retrospective study evaluating the impact of vaccination on sheep mortality during BTV-3 circulation (the Netherlands)	Trade names not specified [Inactivated (dead), Monovalent]	Mortality / Fatal Disease in herds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adult sheep mortality in vaccinated flocks compared to unvaccinated flocks [IRR = 0.65, 95% CI = 0.6 - 0.8] Lamb mortality [IRR = 0.82, 95% CI = 0.69 - 0.97]. Mortality incidence compared to non BTV-3 period in unvaccinated flocks [IRR = 5.2, 95% CI 4.3-6.3] and fully vaccinated flocks [IRR = 3.4, 95% CI =2.9 - 4]. 	Vaccination against BTV-3 significantly reduced mortality in both sheep and lambs, but overall mortality incidence was elevated across both vaccinated and non-vaccinated flocks during epidemic.	(Dijkstra et al., 2025)	
	Cattle	Retrospective field study (the Netherlands)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Bluevac [Vaccine Type: Inactivated (dead); Monovalent] Syvazul [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent] Bultavo [Inactivated (dead)] 	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Bluevac: Proportion of test positive samples [OR = 1.05, 95% CI = 0.25 - 4.48]. Syvazul: Proportion of test positive samples [OR = 0.38, 95% CI= 0.09 - 1.56]. Bultavo: Proportion of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Bluevac and Syvazul vaccines, no statistically significant difference in proportion of test positive samples between vaccinated and non-vaccinated herds. For Bultavo vaccine, the proportion of test positive samples was significantly lower in vaccinated herds. 	(Everts et al., 2025)	

					test positive samples [OR = 0.03, 95% CI = 0.01 - 0.07].		
Cattle	Retrospective cost-benefit study based on field data (Belgium)	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead)]	Association between time of vaccination and serology	>3 months since first injection (versus less than 3 months) [OR= 0.6 (95% CI 0.34-1.07)]	No significant association between time from vaccination and seropositivity. Not possible to compare exposed to not exposed as all cattle were vaccinated.	(Cargnel et al., 2019)	
Sheep	Stochastic model using 2007 outbreak data in US (Wyoming)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Number of morbidities and mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No vaccination: The average number of morbidities = 285; mortalities = 167. Vaccination: Morbidities = 46; mortalities = 27. 	Morbidity and mortality are reduced in vaccinated herds compared to non-vaccinated herds.	(Munsick et al., 2017)	
Sheep and cattle	Stochastic transmission model using 2007 outbreak data in UK	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sheep: Vaccination reduced infection prevalence; 95% coverage for 5 years eradicated infection. Cattle: Vaccination reduced infection prevalence; 95% coverage for 5 years led to very low persistence (<100 cases) but no eradication. For both species, stopping vaccination after 1-3 years caused re-emergence but with lower infection prevalence than without vaccination. 	<p>In sheep, vaccination reduced infection prevalence, with high long-term coverage eradicating the disease</p> <p>In cattle, vaccination reduced infection but did not eradicate disease.</p>	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2017)	

Goat and sheep	Retrospective field study (Italy)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	Association to disease in farms that vaccinates prophylactically [OR = 0.016, 95% CI = 0.009 - 0.027]	Significant association between vaccination and deceleration in disease spread.	(Loi et al., 2017)
Sheep	Field study (Spain)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	Association to disease when > 90% of sheep on farm vaccinated (versus ≤ 90%) [OR= 0.86, 95% CI 0.65-1.13]	Non-significant association between proportion of vaccinated animals on farm and disease status.	(Pascual-Linaza et al., 2014)
Cattle, Goat, Sheep	Retrospective field study (France)	Zulvac 1 bovis/ovis [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	Average velocity of BTv-1 spread: 1.7 km/day lower (~2x) in municipalities with vaccinated animals, than in municipalities without (p < 0.001).	Vaccination was negatively associated with velocity of BTv-1 spread	(Pioz et al., 2014)
Cattle	Retrospective field study (France)	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	Association of vaccination status with testing positive: Vaccinated in June 2008 rather than during epidemic peak [OR = 0.4, p = 0.001]	Significant association between vaccination status and risk of BTv-abortion.	(Zanella et al., 2012)
Cattle	Retrospective field study (Switzerland)	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	Vaccination coverage (geo additive model): posterior mean = -0.06, 95% CI -0.99-1.01	The effect of vaccination coverage became stronger when the farm altitude was accounted for, suggesting that other factors than solely vaccination influence the probability of a unit being infected with BTv-8	(Willgert et al., 2011)
Sheep, goats and cattle	Retrospective field study of an epidemic (Germany)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	1,070 total new cases (sheep, goats and cattle) in 2008 compared to 79,512 case reports in 2007.	Incidence decreased considerably in sheep, goats and cattle under mass vaccination campaign in 2008	(Conraths et al., 2009)
Cattle and sheep	Transmission model using 2006-2007 outbreak data	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	Association between vaccine uptake and risk of outbreak [OR = 0.969 (95% C = 0.966-0.972]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The probability of an outbreak was reduced by increased vaccine uptake. 	(Sumner et al., 2013)

		in Northern EU				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Widespread reactive vaccination resulted in the lowest levels of morbidity. Pre-emptive vaccination reduced the probability of an outbreak occurring. 	
	Cattle and sheep	Transmission model using 2006-2007 outbreak data in Northern EU	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Absence of vaccination: severe outbreaks (especially during warmer temperatures) Vaccination: reduction of incidence, outbreak size, extent of spread Greatest impact of vaccination when high coverage (95%) but some spread still occurs 	<p>Risk of disease spread is greatest during warmer temperatures, with vaccination predicted to reduce the severity of epidemics.</p> <p>The largest impact seen with high (95%) vaccine uptake, but disease is not eradicated.</p>	(Szmaragd, Wilson, et al., 2010)
	Cattle	Retrospective field study (France)	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vaccination status (Not vaccinated; Ref=Compulsory (2009/2010)): OR = 0.04, 95% CI = 0 - 0.1 Vaccination status (Voluntary only; Ref=Compulsory (2009/2010)): [OR = 0.2, 95% CI = 0.1 - 0.2] 	Significant association between vaccination status and odds of seropositivity	(Courtejoie et al., 2018)
	Cattle and sheep	Stochastic transmission model for Scotland using published literature for	Trade name not specified [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent BTV-8 vaccine]	Mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cattle border vaccination: Sheep deaths reduced by up to 90% by vaccinating cattle alone. Sheep border vaccination: Similar 	Targeted vaccine interventions can greatly reduce BTV spread. Vaccination can have the greatest impact on reducing BTV infections in sheep when administered to cattle	(Bessell et al., 2016)

		parameter estimates			<p>reduction in sheep infections as cattle border vaccination but requires vaccination of over 3 times the number of animals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary vaccination by 25% of farms: results in a mean reduction in sheep infections of up to 123,000. Sheep deaths reduced from 104,679 to 41,583 • Voluntary vaccination by 50% or 75% of farms: further reduction in sheep infections and mortalities. 			
	Cattle	Stochastic transmission model for Scotland using published literature for parameter estimates	[Vaccine Type: NA; Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	NA	Vaccination reduced the size and duration of outbreaks, effective in reducing the number of affected premises and the extent of spread, as well as increasing the number of outbreaks dying out. Preventive vaccination (in April) was more effective than reactive (July-Sep) vaccination. It also significantly reduces the morbidity and mortality in both sheep and cattle.	(Szmaragd, Gunn, et al., 2010)	
	Ruminant species	Field study (Italy)	[Vaccine Type: NA; BTV-2 monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 97% coverage reduced disease cases in Sardinia (6090 outbreaks in 2001-2002 vs 10 outbreaks in 2002-2003) 	High vaccination coverage led to a significant reduction of clinical disease.	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2007)	

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 87% coverage eradicated disease cases in Tuscany (158 outbreaks in 2001-2002 vs 0 outbreaks in 2002-2003) The number of outbreaks in 2002-2003 correlated to the level of vaccination in each region (Spearman's $\rho = -0.9150$, $p < 0.0001$). 			
	Cattle, goat, sheep	Retrospective field study (Italy)	[Vaccine Type: NA; BTV-1 monovalent]	Clinical Illness	Animals are vaccinated in the farm [OR = 0.076, 95% CI 0.065-0.089,]	High proportion of BTV-1 vaccinated animals is protective	(Cappai et al., 2018)	
<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i>	Dog	Retrospective field study (Maine, USA)	OspA vaccine [Recombinant (subunit vaccines)]	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Probability of infection in incompletely vaccinated dogs compared to fully vaccinated dogs [RR = 21.4, Min-Max = 14.8 - 52.1]. Preventative Fractions: 95.3% (Min – Max= 93.29 - 98.08%). 	Vaccination was associated with a lower probability of infection.	(Eschner & Mugnai, 2015)	Two field studies demonstrated vaccine association with lower probability of infection.
	Dog	Retrospective field study (Rhode Island, USA)	Recombitek, Merial [Recombinant (subunit vaccines)]	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 60/840 dogs vaccinated were seropositive, but only 1 dog had completed the vaccine protocol, showing low quantitative titer and no symptoms. 	The implementation of the vaccination program led to a marked decrease in the number of dogs testing positive for the infection-specific C6 antibody.	(Hebert & Eschner, 2010)	

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seroprevalence decrease after vaccination program implementation: from 11% (baseline) to 0% 			
Bovine ephemeral fever virus (BEFV)	Cattle	Prospective field study (Israel)	ULTRAVAC BEF VACCINE [Live attenuated; Monovalent]	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccine effectiveness: 60 % (95% CI = 38 – 77%) • Difference between vaccinated (0%) and non-vaccinated (2.6%) mortality (p=0.1). 	A vaccine effectiveness of 60% was found. No statistical differences between vaccinated and non-vaccinated mortality.	(Gleser et al., 2023)	<p>Across these studies, vaccine efficacy varies significantly based on dosage and formulation, ranging from negligible impact after two doses to 50–60%.</p> <p>While vaccination can delay infection onset, immunity often wanes quickly, requiring high coverage (> 40%) rates to successfully shift disease patterns to less frequent disease incidences. The data suggests that while the vaccines provide a degree of protection, their success is heavily dependent on the specific vaccine type, consistent boosting, and achieving broad population coverage.</p>
	Cattle	Prospective field study (Israel)	ETM MONTANIDE ISA 206 VG (water-in-oil-in-water) [Inactivated (dead)]	NA	<u>Vaccine effectiveness</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 doses: 2% (95% CI = 1.4 – 17%). • 3-4 doses: 47.5% (95% CI = 36 – 57%) 	The administration of two doses did not provide protection. Protection of 50% was provided only after administration of 3 doses of vaccine.	(Aziz-Boaron et al., 2014)	
	Cattle	Prospective field study (Taiwan)	Formaldehyde-inactivated BEFV vaccine [trade name not specified] [Inactivated (dead)]	History of Exposure	NA	In reactive vaccination following an outbreak, vaccine-induced immunity was partially protective against BEF. Vaccinated animals appeared to have been infected later than the unvaccinated during the outbreak.	(Wang et al., 2001)	
	Cattle	Retrospective field study (Japan)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With low vaccination coverage (1–40%), disease cases appeared in clusters (cases occurred close together in the same areas) • With higher vaccination coverage (41–80%), cases were more spread out and occurred more sporadically, rather than forming clear clusters 	(Ogawa et al., 1993)	

	Cattle	Prospective field study (Australia)	Quil A vaccine [Live attenuated (Strain 9 19 was derived from a field isolate from the 1978 outbreak of BEF in Queensland; Monovalent)]	Clinical Illness	NA	Two doses of Quil A vaccine provided a significantly higher level of protection against natural challenge than other vaccines tested ($p < 0.01$) and no vaccination.	(Vanselow et al., 1995)	
<i>Leishmania infantum (L. infantum)</i>	Dogs	Prospective field study (Brazil)	Leish-tec [Recombinant (subunit) vaccines]	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differences in cumulative incidence of infection between the vaccinated (27%; 40/151) and unvaccinated (42%; 33/78) dogs ($p = 0.016$). 43% of vaccine recipients developed disease over time 	The incidence of infection significantly differed between the vaccinated and unvaccinated dogs. However, this effect didn't last.	(Grimaldi et al., 2017)	A modeling study indicated that vaccination is effective in reducing disease incidence in dog populations, and field study (Grimaldi et al., 2017) found vaccination significantly reduced the overall incidence of infection, however it did not protect from disease progression in susceptible dogs. Another field study (Lopes et al., 2018) comparing Leishmune® and Leish-tec® vaccines, both alone and in combination with insecticide collars, failed to demonstrate statistically significant protection against infection.
	Dogs	Prospective field study (Brazil)	Leishmune® [Subunit vaccine] Leish-tec [Recombinant (subunit) vaccine]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leishmune® vaccine effectiveness: 26.4% Leishmune® vaccine + insecticide-impregnated collar Vaccine effectiveness: 36.5% Leish-tec® vaccine Vaccine effectiveness: 32.8% Leish-tec® vaccine + insecticide-impregnated collar Vaccine effectiveness: 53.8% 	None of the immunogens were sufficiently effective to protect dogs against infection. Performance of the collars impregnated with insecticide tended to be better than vaccination alone (but results were not statistically significant)	(Lopes et al., 2018)	
	Dogs	Transmission model using published	CaniLeish® [Recombinant (subunit) vaccine]	Pathogen Detection	With a 50% or 75% vaccination coverage, the seroprevalence among	The vaccination of dogs is effective to reduce infection and disease	(Seva et al., 2017)	

		literature for parameter estimates (Spain)		(Pathogen Shedding)	dogs decreases from 2.36% to 1.53% and 1.22%, respectively.	among dogs, but not in controlling the infection in other host species (humans, hares, rabbits and cats).		
<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>	Sheep	Prospective field study (Germany)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	History of Exposure Mortality	Difference in shedding in cohort vaccinated than control ($p < 0.02$).	The vaccine reduced the number of vaginal shedders in a naturally infected sheep flock during the following lambing season and is an efficient control measure. However, there was no statistically significant difference in shedding among vaccinated and control cohorts during the next lambing season. Vaccinated cohort had higher total lamb losses than the control group.	(Bauer et al., 2022)	In field studies, vaccination consistently proves effective at reducing the bacterial load and the prevalence of shedding in vaginal mucus, milk, and uterine fluids, particularly when administered to young or previously seronegative animals before pregnancy. While the vaccine significantly reduces abortions and environmental contamination, its efficacy is often limited in animals already pregnant or previously infected, and it rarely achieves a complete elimination of the pathogen without long-term, consistent application
	Goats and sheep	Retrospective field study (the Netherlands)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	After implementation of the risk mitigating measures (vaccination, culling and strict hygiene - biosecurity) [IRR = 0.14, 95% CI = 0.05-0.44]	After implementation of the risk mitigating measures a significant decrease of infection was seen.	(Vellema et al., 2021)	
	Cattle	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difference in milk shedders: from 9% to 1.2% Uterine fluid samples negative after vaccination. Seroconversion rate 8.6% (first year after vaccination) and 0% (second year) in control group. 	The proportion of shedder animals through uterine fluids and milk progressively decreased after vaccination and no new infection occurred during the study period.	(Piñero et al., 2014)	
	Sheep	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	Cburnetii-abortions Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After whole flock vaccination, proportion of animals aborting decreased in both 	No significant effect of vaccination on risk of shedding nor on bacterial load was found. Vaccine did not provide a complete Coxiella suppression after 3 years but was effective in protecting yearlings.	(Astobiza et al., 2013)	

					<p>ewes (2.0%) and yearlings (1.8%).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effect of vaccination on risk of shedding: $p = 0.15$ • Effect of vaccination on bacterial load: $p = 0.29$ 			
	Cattle	Prospective field study (France)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	History of Exposure Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between vaccination and shedding: [OR = 0.15, CI 95% = 0.03 - 0.85] • For seronegative nulliparous heifers vaccinated before artificial insemination [OR = 0.17, CI 95% = 0.04 - 0.67] 	Vaccination was significantly associated with a reduction in the odds of infection.	(Taurel et al., 2012)	
	Sheep	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of shedders before and after vaccination: 63.2% to 10.1% ($p < 0.05$) and no shedders in the last two seasons. • Difference in mean bacterial loads excreted between the vaccinated and controls: $p > 0.05$ • Environmental samples: 3 DNA positive out of 18. positive aerosols. 	Vaccination reduced shedding especially in ewes and yearlings, but <i>C. burnetii</i> still persisted in the environment.	(Astobiza et al., 2011b)	

	Cattle	Stochastic epidemic model for France using published literature for parameter estimates	Phase I vaccine [Inactivated (dead)]	Clinical Illness Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario 1 (yearly vaccination of cows and heifers for 10 years) reduced environmental bacterial load and abortions over the entire period, reaching almost 0. Scenario 2 (vaccination for 3 years lifelong and short-term immunity) shedder prevalence, abortions and environmental bacterial load rebounded after vaccination ceased Scenario 3 (vaccination of heifers only for 10 years) was slower but also reaching almost 0. 	Under vaccination scenarios, extinction rate varied from 8 to 97%. All three strategies reduced shedders, environmental bacterial load, and abortions. Yearly vaccination was the most effective scenario.	(Courcoul et al., 2011)	
	Goats and sheep	Retrospective field study (the Netherlands)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<p><u>Vaccine efficacy:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uterine samples: In young animals: = 98%; In old animals = 90% Vaginal samples: In young animals = 57%; In old animals = 28% Milk sample = 72%. <p><u>Hazard ratio to test positive if vaccinated:</u></p>	Vaccination significantly reduced the percentage of animals in which bacteria were detected and bacterial load in uterine fluid, vaginal swabs, and milk. Reduced prevalence was most prominent in uterine fluid and in young animals	(Hogerwerf et al., 2011)	

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uterine fluid: [HR = 0.49, 95% CI 0.34-0.70] • Vaginal mucus: [HR = 0.34, 95% CI 0.28-0.42] • Milk:[HR = 0.54, 95% CI 0.39-0.75] 		
Red deer	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac® [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccination did not significantly change the proportion of animals shedding in milk and vaginal secretions (p > 0.05). • Significant reduction deer shedding in feces (but not the bacterial burden) in both the vaccinated and control groups. 	(Gonzalez-Barrio et al., 2017)	
Sheep	Retrospective field study (Tunisia)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	History of Exposure, Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	Association between vaccination and test positivity [OR = 0.114, 95% CI = 0.014 - 0.953]	Vaccination significantly reduces the odds of infection.	(Barkallah et al., 2018)	
Cattle	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Subfertility (>3 AI) Early fetal loss (before day 90 of pregnancy)	<p>Association between vaccination and subfertility: [OR = 0.4, 95% CI = 0.2 - 0.8]</p> <p>Association between vaccination and early fetal loss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seronegative vaccinated [OR = 1.2, 95% CI = 1.1 - 2.1] • Seronegative control [OR = 3.2, 95% CI = 1.1 - 4.2] • Seropositive control [OR = 1.2, 95% CI = 1.1 - 3.3] 	Vaccination reduces subfertility and early fetal loss in dairy cows.	(Garcia-Ispierto et al., 2015)	

	Goats	Prospective field study (France)	Coxevac®; CEVA [Inactivated (dead) (phase I); Monovalent]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average difference in adjusted means between vaccinated and control: 1.55 log₁₀ bacteria per swab (p = 0.04). • Vaginal shedding levels depended on parity (p < 0.01). Average difference between groups was 0.54 and 1.16 log₁₀ bacteria/swab for adults (p = 0.06) and primiparous (p < 0.01). • Among primiparous: 1.81 log₁₀ when females were initially susceptible 	Vaccination did not prevent infection under high infection exposure but induced an overall decrease in shedding level, although the impact depends on parity.	(de Cremoux et al., 2012)	
	Sheep	Prospective field study (Spain)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead) (phase I vaccine); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flock 1. Vaccinated ewes showed a marginally lower shedding rate (59.7%; 37/62) than controls (75.0%; 21/28) (p = 0.07). • Flock 2. Vaccinated ewes had a slightly higher shedding rate (10.3%; 7/68) than controls (7.4%; 2/27), but not significantly. 	Vaccination did not significantly reduce shedding.	(Astobiza et al., 2011a)	
	Cattle	Prospective field study (France)	Coxevac [Inactivated (dead); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of shedders in the vaccinated when nonpregnant, vaccinated when 	Vaccination has a significant effect on shedding only when implemented in a non-pregnant animal.	(Guatteo et al., 2008)	

					<p>pregnant and placebo groups was 6.9%, 28.1% and 27.9%, respectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When vaccinated when not pregnant, an animal had 0.21 ($P < 0.05$) times probability of becoming a shedder than an animal receiving placebo. An animal which was vaccinated when pregnant had a similar probability of becoming shedder than an animal receiving placebo: $HR = 0.90$; $P \geq 0.05$. 			
Eastern equine encephalitis virus (EEEV)	Equines	Outbreak (Michigan, USA)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	Association between annual vaccination and clinical illness [OR = 0.14, 95% CI 0.04-0.51]	Vaccination significantly decreases the odds of infection.	(Ross & Kaneene, 1995)	
Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV)	Pig	Transmission model using 2009 serological data from Bangladesh	[Vaccine Type: NA]	History of Exposure	Depending on assumption of yearly vaccine coverage: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50% of pigs = 82% case incidence reduction. 75% of pigs = 89% reduction. 25% of pig = 61% reduction. 	Vaccination decreases the risk of infection.	(Khan et al., 2014)	
Lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV)	Cattle	Field study (Vietnam)	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Pathogen Detection (Pathogen Shedding)	Association between lack of vaccination and infection [OR = 6.21, 95% CI = 2.01-19.19]	Vaccination significantly decreases the odds of infection.	(Huyen et al., 2025)	In field and modelling studies vaccination was highly effective in controlling LSDV,

	Cattle	Field study (Egypt)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sheep pox vaccine [Vaccine Type: NA] 2. Neethling vaccine [Vaccine Type: NA] 	Clinical Illness Mortality	<p>Association between vaccine status and clinical illness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unknown vaccine status (ref - vaccinated): [OR = 17.14, 95% CI 9.26-31.7] • Unvaccinated (ref - vaccinated) [OR = 8.5, 95% CI 4.48-16.14] <p>Association between vaccine status and death:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unknown vaccine status (ref - vaccinated) [OR = 23.24, 95% CI = 4.38-123.3] • Unvaccinated (ref - vaccinated) [OR = 54.71, 95% CI = 11.11-269.40] 	Unvaccinated and animals with unknown vaccination status exhibited the highest numbers of disease cases and deaths. Sheep-pox vaccine showed 2 LSD-related deaths and had more disease cases compared Neethling strain vaccine (Sheep pox 26 vs 3 Neethling clinical cases)	(Elsheikh et al., 2024)	significantly reducing infection risk, disease severity, and mortality rates. However, vaccine effectiveness varied by region and strain.
	Cattle	Cost study using published data (South Africa)	LSD RVF 2-in -1 vaccine [trade name not specified] [Vaccine Type: NA; Polyvalent]	Cost-benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net present value vaccination > 0 • Internal rate of return vaccination > 0 • Benefit-cost ratio > 1 	The financial benefits generated by vaccination outweigh the total costs of implementation, indicating the positive impact of vaccination.	(Mdlulwa et al., 2018)	
	Cattle	Retrospective study of outbreak in Turkey	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	Association between vaccination and LSD [OR = 0.13, 95% CI 0.05-0.34]	Vaccination significantly reduced the risk of clinical illness.	(Ince & Türk, 2020)	
	Cattle	Field study (Ethiopia)	Kenyan sheep pox virus strain vaccine (KS1 O-180) [Vaccine	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between vaccination and clinical illness [OR = 	Vaccination significantly decreased the risk clinical illness, reduced the susceptibility to disease but	(Molla et al., 2017)	

			Type: Live attenuated]		<p>0.49, 95% CI = 0.37 - 0.64]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between only vaccination and lower severity score [OR=0.68, 95% CI = 0.49 - 0.96]. • Probability of developing moderate and severe disease (0.89 unvaccinated vs 0.84 vaccinated) • Vaccine efficacy for susceptibility (Coefficient = 0.54, 95%CI = 0.44 - 0.66); Vaccine efficacy for infectiousness (Coefficient = 1.83, 95% CI =1.28 - 2.61) • Estimated reduction in Reproduction Ratio (R) by vaccination = 0.98 (95% CI = 0.73 - 1.33) 	<p>increased infectiousness. The reduction in Reproduction Ratio (R) for vaccinated cattle was not significant.</p> <p>Kenyan sheep pox strain vaccine had poor efficacy in protecting cattle populations against the pathogen</p>	
Cattle	Retrospective field study (Greece)	(Onderstepoort Biological Products, South Africa) [Live attenuated]	Clinical Illness	<p>After vaccination: outbreaks reduced from 83 to no new outbreaks. Nine later outbreaks limited to non-vaccinated holdings.</p>	<p>No new outbreaks were observed after vaccination.</p>	(Tasioudi et al., 2016)	
Cattle	Retrospective field study of outbreaks in the Balkan region	1. Non-EEA: SGPV vaccine [Sheep and goatpox strain Live		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field: Outbreaks were reported until the end of 2018 in Turkey, despite vaccination (heterologous vaccine) campaigns 	<p>Monovalent vaccines result in sufficient protection, contrarily to polyvalent vaccines.</p>	(EFSA, 2019)	

		Transmission model using 2016 outbreak data from the Balkan region	attenuated; Polyvalent] 2. Non-EEA: Poxvac, Vetat [Sheep and goatpox strain Live attenuated; Polyvalent] 3. EEA: LSD vaccine [Live attenuated; Monovalent]		using SGPV vaccine since 2014. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balkan region countries achieved a mean vaccination (homologous vaccine) coverage of 78% and no outbreaks were reported in 2018 in the region Modelling: Assuming a VE of 62.5%, the median level of vaccine coverage to control the outbreak was 52.5% (CI 7.3-91.7%). Assuming a VE of 76.5%, the median level of vaccine coverage to control the outbreak was 43.6% (CI 5.9-83.8%). 		
	Cattle	Transmission model using 2015-2016 outbreak data from Albania, Bulgaria and Greece	[Live attenuated; Homologous]	Clinical Illness	NA	In the absence of new introductions, 2-3 years of vaccination at a coverage of 90% is most likely to be sufficient to eliminate LSDV from the population. 2-5 years of vaccination at coverage of 70% is most likely to be sufficient to eliminate LSDV from the population.	(EFSA, 2018b)
	Cattle	Retrospective field study (Vietnam)	LSD vaccine (Neethling strain) [Live attenuated]	Clinical Illness	Association between unvaccinated status and LSD [OR = 5.52, 95% CI = 3.62 - 8.44]	Vaccination significantly reduces the risk of clinical illness.	(Bich et al., 2024)
	Cattle	Bayesian time-series model using	trade name not specified [Live attenuated (Live	Clinical Illness	119% decrease in cases after vaccination (relative	Vaccination significantly reduces incidence.	(Punyapornwithaya et al., 2023)

		2021 outbreak data from Thailand	attenuated homologous LSD vaccines (Neethling strain)); Monovalent]		effect) (95% CI: -121 to -38%, p = 0.04)		
	Cattle	Transmission model using 2016 outbreak data from Albania	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vaccine effectiveness: 76,5% (95% CI = 71.8 - 80.6%) 	Vaccination has a significant impact on infection risk, and the vaccine effectiveness was 76%.	(Gubbins et al., 2020)
	Cattle	Retrospective field study of the Balkan region (Macedonia, Albania, Greece, Bulgaria, Montenegro, Serbia)	Neethling vaccine [Live attenuated, Monovalent, (LUMPYVAX MSD or OBP vaccine)]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall average Vaccine effectiveness across all countries: 79.8% (95% CI = 73.2 - 84.7) VE range: 62.5% - 97.3% 	Vaccination has a significant impact on infection risk, and the overall vaccine effectiveness was 80%.	(Klement et al., 2020)
	Cattle	Transmission model using 2012-2015 outbreak data from the Middle East region	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Clinical Illness	Inferred difference effective reproductive number after vaccination (Rt) from 22.2, (95% CI = 15.2 - 31.5) to 0.4 (95% CI = 0.3 - 0.5]	Sharp drop of Israel's inferred Rt value indicates the 2013 vaccination campaign reduced the risk of transmission.	(Alkhamis & VanderWaal, 2016)
	Cattle	Retrospective field study, outbreaks in Balkan region	[Live attenuated; Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<p>Vaccine effectiveness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Albania: 62.5% (95% CI = 56.9 - 67.4) Bulgaria: 95.6%, (95% CI = 86.6 - 98.5%) + no outbreaks were reported in Bulgaria in 2017. 	A higher proportion of non-vaccinated farms experienced an outbreak, compared to vaccinated, indicating the significant impact on infection risk and the overall vaccine effectiveness between 63% and 96%.	(EFSA, 2018a)

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greece: 84% (95% CI = 73 - 91%) 			
Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV)	Cattle	Cost study using published data (South Africa)	LSD RVF 2-in -1 vaccine [trade name not specified] [Vaccine Type: NA; Polyvalent]	Cost-benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Net present value vaccination > 0 Internal rate of return vaccination > 0 Benefit-cost ratio > 1 	The financial benefits generated by vaccination outweigh the total costs of implementation, indicating the positive impact of vaccination.	(Mdlulwa et al., 2018)	In modeling studies, vaccination is highly effective, particularly when implemented proactively or targeting cattle to provide cross-species protection. Strategies like biannual vaccination or rapid response achieved up to 90% impact, whereas delayed or slow efforts diminish effectiveness.
	Cattle, sheep	Transmission model using 2006-2007 outbreak data from Kenya		Clinical Illness Cumulative incidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vaccine coverage 25%: reduction incidence >22%. Timing of the vaccination: vaccinating at outbreak onset compared to 24 weeks: 3%- 9% reduction in cumulative incidence in cattle and 5%-7% in sheep. Biannual vaccination: >90% reduction incidence at coverage of 20%-40%. Annual vaccination: >90% with coverage of 30%-65%. 	Vaccinating cattle alone in the population confers protection to both cattle and sheep. Targeting sheep alone confers protection to sheep population only. Varying vaccination timing affects the cumulative disease incidence, with earlier vaccination having greatest impact	(Gachohi et al., 2016)	
	Cattle, goats and sheep	Transmission model using 2009-2012 outbreak data from East Africa	[Vaccine Type: NA]	Mortality		Changing the timing of RVF vaccination across the year shows little variability in deaths.	(Sottile et al., 2021)	
	Cattle	Transmission model using published	[Vaccine Type: NA]		NA	A 30-fold reduction in mortality was associated with vaccination programs. The reduction is greater if	(McMahon et al., 2014)	

		data from East Africa				the vaccine response time is less than 2 weeks.		
	Cattle, goat, sheep	Stochastic transmission model using outbreak data from Mayotte (2018-2019) and Tanzania (2007)	[Vaccine Type: NA]		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rates of 200 or 2000 animals/day halt epidemic within 1 year; 20 animals/day leads to epidemic continuation for >2 years. The number of infections <3% if the vaccination is conducted >30 days prior incursion with 200 animals/day vaccinated or if <60 days post incursion with vaccinating 2000 animals/day. 	Vaccination is more effective when applied before the start of the epidemic and quickly implemented throughout the population.	(EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare, 2020)	
<i>Trypanosoma vivax (T. vivax)</i>	Cattle	Prospective field study (Kenya)	Flagellar pocket (Fp) antigen from <i>Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense</i> [Recombinant (subunit vaccines); Monovalent]	Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment 1: Prevalence of infection in untreated controls, samorin treated (prophylactic drug), and 20 Fp antigen inoculated: 58%, 41% and 26% (p<0.001). Experiment 2: untreated controls Fp antigen inoculated 6months: 22% and 9% (p<0.005). Experiment 3: untreated controls and Fp antigen inoculated with 	Vaccination leads to significant lower infection rates compared to non-vaccination.	(Mkunza et al., 1995)	A field study by Mkunza et al. (1995) showed that vaccination leads to significant lower infection rates compared to non-vaccination, outperforming the prophylactic drug Samorin.

					<p>ovalbumin as the carrier 15 months: 13% and 0.9% ($p < 0.001$).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall prevalence of the infection for the entire period of more than 21 months untreated and immunized cattle: 38% and 10% ($p < 0.001$). 			
West Nile virus (WNV)	Horse	Retrospective field study (Florida, USA)	Formalin-inactivated whole virion vaccine	History of Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association between vaccination 2 weeks to 6 months and infection: [OR = 0.06, 95% CI = 0.04-0.82] Association between two doses vaccination and infection [OR = 0.48, 95% CI = 0.01-0.69] Association between protective vaccination and infection [OR = 0.18, 95% CI = 0.09-0.98] 	Vaccination is associated with a statistically significant reduction in the odds of infection group, with the strongest protection seen in the "2 weeks to 6 months" window	(Rios et al., 2009)	In field studies, vaccination significantly reduces the risk of clinical WNV infection in horses and increases survival odds for those that do contract the disease. Unvaccinated horses are about twice as likely to die, while those following recommended vaccination protocols see a reduction in case fatality rates.
	Horse	Prospective field study (California, USA)	West Nile Innovator, Fort Dodge Laboratories, Fort Dodge, IA, USA [Inactivated (dead)] Canarypox recombinant Recombitek Equine West Nile virus vaccine,	Clinical Illness	Difference in proportion clinical cases among unvaccinated horses compared to vaccinated (5.4% vs 0%; $p = 0.035$)	Vaccination is associated with a statistically significant reduction in clinical cases.	(Gardner et al., 2007)	

			Merial Limited, Duluth, GA, USA [Recombinant (subunit vaccines)]				
Horse	Retrospective field study (Texas, USA)	inactivated WNV vaccine [Inactivated (dead)]		Clinical Illness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vaccination prior to disease onset increased survival odds by 1.8 times (p = 0.005) • 44% reduction in mortality risk • 68.9% of disease cases were unvaccinated within previous 12 months 	Vaccination prior to disease onset significantly increases survival odds.	(Ward et al., 2006)
Horse	Retrospective field study of an outbreak in North Dakota (USA)	[Vaccine Type : NA]		Clinical Illness, Mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between time since vaccination and outcome: P = 0.049 • Significantly different case fatality rates (14% vaccinated vs 34% unvaccinated 34%, p < 0.001). • Association between vaccination not following manufacturer's instructions and death [OR = 0.32, 95% CI= 0.15 - 0.68] • Association between vaccination with instructions and death [OR, 0.062 = 95% CI 0.007 - 0.58] 	<p>Horses with a relatively shorter time-since-vaccination interval are significantly more likely to die or be euthanized than those with a longer time-since-vaccination interval.</p> <p>Vaccinated horses had significantly lower case fatality.</p>	(Schuler et al., 2004)

	Horse	Retrospective field study of an outbreak in Nebraska and Colorado (USA)	[Vaccine Type : NA]	Clinical Illness, Mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between non vaccination and death [OR = 2.1, 95% CI = 1 - 4.5] • Association between vaccination after onset of signs and death [OR = 0.2, 95% CI = 0.03 - 1.6] 	After controlling for other factors associated with death, equids that were not vaccinated were 2.1 times more likely to die.	(Salazar et al., 2004)	
	Horse	Retrospective field study of an outbreak in Saskatchewan (USA)	West Nile Innovator [Inactivated (dead)]	Pathogen Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Association between non-vaccination and infection [OR= 22.5, 95% CI 3 - 168.5] (individual-level) and [OR = 48.8, 95% CI 4.8 – 493] (holding-level) • Association between partial vaccination: [OR = 20.8, 95% CI = 2.8 -157.3] (individual-level) and [OR = 15.2, 95% CI = 1.5 -152.5] (holding-level) 	Non-vaccinated horses have significantly higher odds of infection.	(Epp et al., 2007)	

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